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Session A

**PLANT GENETICS,
BREEDING AND
PROTECTION**

SOURCES OF RESISTANCE AT SUNFLOWER DOWNY MILDEW

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Pathogen *Plasmopara halstedii* causes low seed yield at sunflower genotypes, in year with high precipitation and low temperature in first stage of development of sunflower plant. In year 2021, at Fundulea location, sunflower downy mildew has a big attack degree of infection in first stage of development, due to weather conditions and in year 2022, degree attack was very low. In year 2021, only differential line for downy mildew HA 288 (gene *Pl₂*) from Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops Novi Sad, Serbia and differential lines RHA419 (gene *Pl_{Arg}*), accession PI 619204 and HA-R5 (gene *Pl₁₃*), accession PI 650763 from United States National Plant Germplasm System, has 0% attack degree of pathogen *Plasmopara halstedii*.

In year 2022, only differential line for downy mildew RHA274(gene *Pl₂/Pl₂₁*), accession PI 599759, from United States National Plant Germplasm System and differential lines DM 2 93CA from Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops Novi Sad, Serbia and RHA340 (gene *Pl₈*), HA 335 (gene *Pl₆*), has sunflower plant infected with pathogen *Plasmopara halstedii*. Year 2021 was the reference for selection of resistant sunflower genotypes at downy mildew. In year 2021, in Fundulea location, only three sunflower genotypes created at NARDI Fundulea, SPL 21-2X *Helianthus maximiliani* (F2 generation), SPL 14-3 and 17-3 P. sint, was resistant at races of downy mildew present in this area. These three sunflower genotypes represent sources of resistance at pathogen *Plasmopara halstedii*.

Key words: *Plasmopara halstedii*, genotype, sunflower, differential line, degree attack.

MOLECULAR DIAGNOSIS OF PHYTOPLASMA IN THE WILD TOMATO SPECIES *Solanum habrochaites*

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Phytoplasmas are microorganisms without a cell wall that colonize the phloem of many crops. Diseases of plants caused by phytoplasma lead to decreased yields. In the Republic of Moldova, phytoplasma mainly affects tomato and grapevine. Phytoplasmosis of local tomato is associated with the presence of the pathogen ‘*Candidatus* Phytoplasma solani’. The infection causes dwarfism of the plants, the sepals are completely joined, the petals are green, the flowers are often sterile, and the fruits, if formed, are small. All this leads to a decrease in agricultural production up to 70-100%.

The aim of the research was to test the presence of ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ in the wild tomato *Solanum habrochaites*. Molecular diagnosis of this pathogen was made during two years, 2019 and 2020. The determination of phytoplasma was carried out on 10 individual plants in both years. In 2019, the analysis of the presence of phytoplasma was made during the entire vegetation season: in July, August and September. In 2020, this research was realized in August and September. DNA was isolated using express method by boiling of thin sections of tomato peduncles in alkaline solution. Nested-PCR analysis was made using specific to ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ chaperonine primers. Molecular diagnosis of plants of the wild tomato species *Solanum habrochaites* did not reveal the presence of the ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ during both growing seasons of the study: neither in 2019 nor in 2020. This result in the lack of ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ in the plants of the wild species in conditions of both years allowed to assume the high resistance of *Solanum habrochaites*. To evidence this, it was necessary, firstly, to confirm the presence of ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ in the tomato field and, secondly, to compare data obtained on the wild species *Solanum habrochaites* with the results of the diagnostics of phytoplasma spread in plants of the species *Solanum lycopersicum*. So, plants of four local varieties of *Solanum lycopersicum* were analyzed at the end of the growing seasons (mid-September) of 2019 and 2020. The scheme of molecular procedures was the same as for the wild species. It was found that the total proportion of plants affected by phytoplasma in the four tomato varieties in 2019 was significant and reached 69.6%. On the contrary, the percentage of infected plants of these four varieties of tomato in 2020 was lower, amounting to only 14.5% at the end of the growing season. Thus, a different level of phytoplasma distribution was registered in *Solanum lycopersicum* plants in 2019 and 2020. Plants of *Solanum habrochaites* were resistant to phytoplasma in both years of the study, manifesting the absence of the infection. Resistance of this wild species to ‘*Ca. P. solani*’ may be due to some morpho-physiological characteristics. First of all, a dense pubescence of stems and leaves of *Solanum habrochaites* is a mechanical barrier for insect vectors. In addition, the eventual production of plant-specific repellents could prevent the infestation through insects. Therefore, *Solanum habrochaites* can be used by breeders for comparative evaluation and creation of tomato varieties and hybrids resistant to phytoplasma.

Key words: *Solanum habrochaites*, pathogen, Nested-PCR analysis, varieties.

**THE GROWTH AND FRUCTIFICATION OF APPLE VARIETIES
DEPENDING ON VARIETY AND THE PRUNING SYSTEM**

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The aim of the research: to find ways to increase the productivity of new apple tree varieties and of fruit quality by developing new methods of tree crown maintenance and pruning. Apple trees, aged 11-12, of Gala Delicious, Golden Delicious and Granny Smith varieties, grafted on M9 rootstock, planted in the meadow of the Dniester River, namely at the Spica-N Agro Farm Cooperative, in the village of Onitcani, the district of Criuleni, served as the object of the research. The orchard had a planting density of 2857 trees/ha.

Two apple tree pruning systems were used during the research period, namely in G1 (the control group) – the maintenance and thinning pruning; G2 – the maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches. The experiment was carried out using four groups of eight trees each. The soil was artificially sown with grass between the rows and ploughed on the rows of trees. The pruning of trees was carried out according to the scheme of the experiment, i.e. pruning that permit to keep the trees in physiological balance of growth and fruiting. The fight against diseases and pests was carried out according to the guidelines issued by the Chisinau Station for Plant Protection and via direct observations made at the weather station directly in the orchard. Foliar application of urea and some micronutrients to fruit trees, i.e. foliar fertilization, as well as balanced fertigation using the drip irrigation as needed, were regularly carried out in the orchards during the vegetation period.

The thinning pruning (G1) allowed for higher annual growth as compared with the maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches (G2). If the main branches are not shortened (G2), but the length of the annual branches decreases, the crown of the tree develops in a balanced and natural way along the height of the tree and are able to form optimal crops for such orchards in a super-intensive system. Leaf area per tree and per unit area was almost the same for both tree pruning methods. The difference in leaf area, depending on the pruning method used, consisted in an increase in leaf area on shoots in G1 and an increase in leaf area on fruit formations in. The Gala Delicious, Granny Smith and Golden Delicious varieties, grafted on the M9 rootstock, were productive; after 11-13 from their planting, they produced between 19.6-48.2 t/ha in 2020, and between 51.0 - 65.4 t/ha in 2019. The Granny Smith variety showed a higher weight of the fruit as opposed to the Gala Delicious and Golden Delicious varieties. The firmness of the fruit, the titratable acidity and the dry soluble matter in the varieties studied are indicators that depend on the biology of the variety and less on the agrotechnics used in the orchard.

The maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches, exerted a major impact on the increase of the number of flower buds, the obtaining of stable yields of 30-40 t/ha, and the generation of a profit from the sale of production of over 100,000 lei/ha with a profitability of about 150%.

Key words: a, productivity, varieties, fruit quality.

THE PRODUCTIVITY OF APPLE ORCHARDS DEPENDING ON VARIETY AND PRUNING SYSTEM

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The aim of the research was to find ways to increase the productivity of apple orchards by developing methods for pruning trees that maintain a physiological balance between growth and fruiting. The research was conducted in the experimental apple orchard of the Spica-N Agro Farm Cooperative in the village of Onitcani, the district of Criuleni. The orchard was planted in 2009 with apple trees of Gala Delicious, Golden Delicious and Granny Smith varieties, grafted on the dwarfing rootstock M9. The orchards were laid out with 1m between trees in the row, and 3.5 m between rows. The tree crowns had the shape of an improved slender spindle.

During the experiment, two pruning methods were studied: G1 – the maintenance and thinning pruning (the control group); G2 – the maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches. The experiment was performed using four groups of eight trees each. The maintenance and thinning pruning (G1 – the control group) was performed according to the methodical guidelines on modern orchards in the Republic of Moldova. The care and phytosanitary protection of the trees were carried out in accordance with the provisions of the technology for growing apple trees. The soil in the orchard was maintained by its artificial grassing and the utilization of herbicides. Foliar application of urea and some micronutrients to fruit trees, i.e. foliar fertilization, as well as fertigation using the drip irrigation as needed, were regularly carried out in the orchards. The apple trees of the studied varieties reached a maximum yield of 18-20 kg/tree in 2019. The trees in G2, were used, produced a higher crop as compared with the control group. When the Gala Delicious apple trees reached the age of eleven, they produced 60.9 t/ha in G1 and 65.4 t/ha in G2. The same legitimacy was registered for the Golden Delicious and Granny Smith varieties, i.e. the harvest increased when the maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches were used. In 2020, the fruit harvest decreased considerably, as opposed to the previous year, and was only between 19.6-48.3 t/ha. The Gala Delicious and Golden Delicious varieties produced higher crops in contrast with the Granny Smith variety. The maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches also increased the fruit production by 5-9 t/ha as compared to the maintenance and thinning pruning used in the control group. In 2021, the fruit yield was influenced not only by the pruning system, but also by the climatic conditions during the flowering of the trees. The Gala Delicious variety produced between 35.9-38.8 t/ha, the Granny Smith variety – between 39.2-42.7 t/ha and the Golden delicious variety – between 27.1-28.3 t/ha.

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that the maintenance and thinning pruning without the shortening of main branches of the apple trees of the Golden Delicious, Gala Delicious and Granny Smith varieties, grafted on the semi-dwarf rootstock M9, is a technological process that is worth using in modern apple orchards.

Key words: apple orchards, productivity, growth, varieties.

EVALUATION OF RESISTANCE TO TOXIGENIC FUNGI IN SEVERAL MAIZE INBRED LINES

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Maize is attacked by a wide range of pathogenic fungi that cause devastating diseases and lead to significant yield losses. Precise identification of fungi in agricultural products is the key aspect of any pest prevention and management program, providing essential information for crop health and food safety. The aim of this paper was to evaluate new maize genotypes based on resistance to fungal phytopathogens. It allows creating the specialized collection within the active corn collection of the Laboratory of Plant Genetic Resources of IGFP.

Twelve new inbred lines obtained from synthetic populations were used in the study. The collection samples were evaluated in the field under climatic conditions of 2021. During harvesting, the number of cobs with symptoms of *Fusarium* spp. infection was determined. The analysis of the obtained data revealed a genotypic difference in the degree of attack and the intensity of disease development. The rate of plants infected with *Fusarium* ear rot ranged from 0 to 100% depending on the genotype. The mean value of the infection rate was 26.3%. The maximum level of plant damage (70% and 100%) was recorded in MAN2425 and MAN2448 respectively, which allowed them to be classified as highly susceptible. Four lines with an infection rate of 30 to 50% (MAN2424, MAN2461, MAN2281 and MAN2451) were considered as the moderately susceptible group. Genotypes with a disease prevalence of less than 30% were classified as poorly susceptible (MAN2308, MAN2459, MAN2526, MAN2413, MAN2452 and MAN2414). Molecular identification of fungi was performed using nested-PCR with a set of primers developed in the Molecular Genetics Laboratory based on genomic sequences, associated with the synthesis of trichothecenes, aflatoxins and fumonisins from the GenBank database. Positive amplification was marked by a band of 152 bp for *A. flavus*, 120 bp for *A. parasiticus*, 147 bp - *F. graminearum*, 179 bp - *F. verticillioides*, 123 - *F. proliferatum*. Thus, all five species of toxigenic fungi were identified in MAN2459 and MAN2461 kernels. *F. proliferatum* was absent, and only *A. flavus*, *F. graminearum* and *F. verticillioides* were identified in MAN2451 kernels. The toxigenic race of *F. graminearum* was absent in MAN2308 and MAN2526 kernels. In two lines (MAN2425 and MAN2452) only toxigenic *A. flavus*, *F. verticillioides* and *F. proliferatum* were identified. Only *F. graminearum* was absent in the MAN2414 line, and in the case of the MAN2413 genotype two *Fusarium* species were absent. *F. graminearum* and *F. proliferatum* were absent in MAN2424 kernels, as well as four species of toxigenic fungi were identified in MAN2448 inbred line.

The most infected corn lines were MAN2459 and MAN2461, in whose kernels 5 species of toxigenic fungi were detected. And the least infected was the MAN2452 line - only *F. verticillioides* was identified in grain samples.

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Key words: *Fusarium* spp., inbred lines, degree of attack, maize, nested-PCR.

**PERFORMAND NEW VARIETIES OF *SALVIA SCLAREA*
(CLARY SAGE)**

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In Moldova, the varieties of hybrid origin of *Salvia sclarea* L., which bloom and produce raw materials and essential oil in the first year of vegetation and the plantations can be exploited three years, are created and homologated. The varieties are distinguished by a high production of raw materials and essential oil, different periods of technical maturity, resistance to drought, frost and wintering. The specificity of the research consists in the creation and implementation of the varieties resistant to frost, winter, diseases, performances that ensure a high productivity and a high quality, thus diminishing the negative consequences of climate change. In the first year of vegetation, the varieties *Ambriela* and *Parfum Perfect* form floral stems which are from 109.5 cm to 120.6cm tall, respectively, with long inflorescences (52.7 to 58.8 cm), compact, with a number of ramifications (14.5 to 18.4). These characters favor the yield structure; contribute to the synthesis and accumulation of large amounts of essential oil. The content of essential oil in the first year of vegetation has values between 1.037% (dry matter) and 1.636% (dry matter). In 2020, under conditions of severe drought, the tested varieties, that were in the second year of vegetation, synthesized and accumulated a high content of essential oil, from 1.320% (dry matter) – the variety *Ambriela*, up to 1.424% (dry matter) the variety *Parfum Perfect*. The quality of essential oil is excellent due to the high content of linalyl acetate and sclareol. The variety *Ambriela* is a complex hybrid with constant heterosis. distinctive by: Physiological properties: Very good resistance to wintering; very high resistance to drought; Resistant to foliar diseases and root system diseases. Quality properties: Essential oil content: First year of vegetation: 0.353% (standard humidity, 70%); 1.175% (dry matter); Second year of vegetation: 0.335% standard humidity; 1.185% dry matter. Major components in essential oil: Linalyl acetate 61.06%, linalool, 8.59%, sclareol, 5.25%.

The variety of *Salvia sclarea* L. *Parfum Perfect* is a triple hybrid with a constant effect of heterosis on a number of quantitative characters, including the essential oil content. Productivity in 2 years of operation of the plantation: inflorescences: 26.9 t/ha (13.8 t/ha, first year; 13,1 t/ha, second year); essential oil content 1.267 -1.424% (dry matter). The productions of essential oil constitute 73.5 kg/ha (8.7 kg/ha, year I; 64.8 kg/ha, year II). Efficiency: 3.8 kg of essential oil per ton of inflorescences.

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Key words: *Salvia sclarea*, hybrid, quantitative characters.

**PECULIARITIES OF STORAGE PROTEIN POLYMORPHISM
IN THE ENDOSPERM OF MUTANT MAIZE LINES**

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The scientific and research school of Professor Andrei Paliu vividly illustrates the effectiveness of using endosperm genes in heterosis breeding of *Zea mays* L. that improve the quality of maize grain. The high-lysine hybrids obtained at the State Agrarian University of Moldova (SAUM) were the optimal model for the development of a new research vector related to the production of tetraploid maize forms containing the opaque-2 (*o2*) gene in their genotype. A new reserve for expanding the spectrum of genetic variability in terms of protein metabolites of maize grain quality was experimentally demonstrated. In the period of 2015-2018 a study was carried out at the heterozygous level of the effect of the influence of polyploidy on the phenotype and expression of specific genes in grain according to the end products of protein metabolism. However, for maize, the success of heterosis breeding for quality is determined primarily by the use of specific parental lines. In the direction under discussion, these are lines that combine gene and genomic mutations, the study of which requires the use of modern methodological tools. Therefore, the main goal of the presented work was to study the features of polymorphism of storage proteins (zeins) of gene (*o2* gene) and genomic mutant (tetraploid) maize lines. 32 maize genotypes, created on the basis of 10 maize lines according to the principle of "unity of differences" (*o2*/normal; 2n/4n), were used as germplasm. The studies were carried out using the storage protein electrophoresis method according to the national standard SM-2003, the FOREZ-2 computer program, the technique of direct and reverse marking of gene and genomic mutations, as well as the principles of quantitative analysis of the mutational effect on zein polymorphism. It has been established that the use of automatically synthesized electrophoretic (EF) spectra from matrices of protein profiles in reciprocal combinations makes it possible to study and interpret the effects of enrichment and elimination of the action of the *o2* gene and colchicine polyploidization on the molecular forms of zein (MPS). The predominant effect of the eliminating (reducing) action of the *o2* gene and the enriching effect of colchicine polyploidization on the zein polymorphism of the endosperm of the studied maize lines was revealed. The prevailing elimination effect of the *o2* gene on the zein fraction of the grain was established: it is most pronounced in the EF zone of medium migration. The elimination effect of colchicine polyploidization according to the protein profiles of the EF spectra is also most clearly manifested in the zone of average migration of molecular forms of zein (MFZs) markers. This fact is of considerable interest for future research in the field of selection at the level of protein marking of maize source material for mutational selection.

Key words: *Zea mays* L., polymorphism, zein, *o2* gene, metabolism.

УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ПО ЗАЩИТЕ ЗЕРНА ОТ ЧЛЕНИСТОНОГИХ В БЕЛАРУСИ

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В Республике Беларусь предпосылками для распространения вредителей запасов в техноценозах зернохранилищ являются потепление климата, наличие зернохранилищ разных конструкций, ограниченный ассортимент препаратов. В связи с этим усовершенствована система мероприятий по защите зерна от членистоногих.

Исследования, проведенные в 2019–2020 гг., показали, что в складских помещениях распространение получили 17 видов вредителей из отрядов Жесткокрылые (*Coleoptera*), Сенокосы (*Psocoptera*), Акариформные клещи (*Acarina*).

Система включает два этапа: подготовка складских помещений до загрузки и защита сельскохозяйственной продукции во время хранения. Она базируется на рациональном использовании препаратов различными способами (влажная и аэрозольная обработка, фумигация) с учетом фитосанитарной ситуации по видовому составу, структуре доминирования вредителей, конструкции (герметичности) зернохранилищ, целевого назначения и способа хранения продукции, температурно-влажностного режима, механизма действия препаратов с антирезистентной направленностью.

Влажная обработка инсектицидами и инсектоакарицидами из химических классов фосфорорганические, комбинированные препараты и пиретроиды обеспечивала биологическую эффективность от насекомых и клещей на уровне 83.9–100 %. Эффективность аэрозольной обработки зависела от способа хранения сельскохозяйственной продукции (в мешках, в насыпи). Фумигация определялась выбором препаратов, нормы расхода, экспозиции с учетом температурного режима. Биологическая эффективность против вредителей составляла 80.5–100 %. Согласно антирезистентной стратегии препараты следует чередовать с учетом чувствительности популяций вредителей к токсикантам.

По результатам проведенных исследований разработана блок-схема мероприятий по защите зерна от вредителей запасов, позволяющая оперативно принимать решения.

Key words: членистоногие, зерна, фумигация, инсектоакарицид, инсектицид, защитные меры.

IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF SUNFLOWER HYBRIDS

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In the face of climate change, the risk of decreasing agricultural production, including sunflower seeds, is increasing. An important role in mitigating climate risks is reserved for the creation, evaluation, and introduction of drought-resistant hybrids. Given that the productivity and quality of the sunflower crop are strongly influenced by genotype, environmental conditions, and their interaction. The aim of this study was to evaluate how sunflower production is affected by the Genotype-Environment interaction.

For this, in the period 2015-2020, 21 sunflower hybrids were studied in five localities on the experimental sectors of the State Commission for Testing Plant Varieties located in different agro-climatic areas of the Republic of Moldova such as Visoca, Pelenia, Băcioi, Grigorievca, and Svetlii.

During the investigated period, two of the investigated years 2015 and 2020 were characterized by droughts of different intensities. If in the dry year 2015 the small amount of precipitation during the vegetation period is partially supplemented by the precipitation in the cold season before the growing season, in 2020, the effects of drought were more pronounced due to insufficient rainfall in the cold season, and higher thermal average.

The best conditions for sunflower growth were in 2017, when an average harvest of 3.36 t / ha was recorded. In 2015 and 2020, the average harvest was 2.99 t / ha and, respectively, - 2.81 t/ha, decreasing by about 13% compared to the average multiannual data.

The two-factors variance analysis identified the relative contributions of the specific climatic conditions of the year on productivity, regardless of the agro-climatic zone of which the given location is part. The average in all five locations of the relative contributions of meteorological conditions of the year in the yield variance is about 38%. It should be noted that the relative contributions of genotype & year interaction in some localities such as Visoca and Svetli exceeds 50%. The relative contributions of the “growing year” factor varies from 51,4% in the North to 26,4% in the South, and the relative contributions of the “location” factor varies from 68.3% in 2020 to 25.3% in 2016. The relative contributions of the „genotype” factor contribution is usually less than 20% in most locations.

So, the meteorological conditions of the location or the growing season and their interaction with the genotype, are the main sources of crop variation.

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Key words: hybrid, productivity, sunflower, drought, growing.

EVALUATION OF PERFORMANT HYBRID HYBRIDS IN DIFFERENT YEARS OF VEGETATION

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The creation and evaluation of prospective hybrid genotypes of *L. angustifolia*, the selection of high-performance hybrids with different maturation terms, which would harmoniously combine special indices of the main biological and production characters as well as increased essential oil content, is of major importance. Research includes prospective hybrids, with remarkable quantitative traits for obtaining new lavender clone varieties.

The basic objective of lavender breeding is to create hybrids with high essential oil content in the raw material. This index varies from 4.022% (dry matter) to 6.042% (dry matter) in the hybrids from the early maturation group, from 4.042% - 6.476% the semi-early hybrids are characterized and from 4.019% to 6.012% - the late group. The most promising prospects for essential oil content were studied during the years 2019-2021. From the set of studied hybrid genotypes, with high essential oil content, 2 genotypes from the maternal forms (Fr.1, Fr.5) and 4 descending hybrids from the maternal forms Fr.8 and Cr.13 were manifested. The essential oil content in the fourth year of vegetation (2019) for lavender F1 hybrids is from 3.988% to 6.344%. Values clearly higher than this character were recorded by the hybrids 1Fr.1-3-2-30V- 5.101% (dry matter), 14Fr.8-5-15-18V-5.453% (dry matter), 4Fr.5S-8-54-5 -5,212% (dry matter), 7Cr.13S-6-12-27-5.226%, 7Cr.13S-6-12-28- 6.344% (dry matter). The content of essential oil in inflorescences in the maternal forms is significantly lower and constitutes 2.508%, 2.600% 2.978% and 3.435% (dry matter) respectively at Cr.13; Fr 5; Fr.1; Fr.8. The variation of the essential oil content in the hybrids evaluated in the fourth year (2020), registers values from 3.988% to the hybrid 4Fr.5S-8-54-10 to 6.344% (s.u.) to the hybrid 7Cr.13S -6-12-28. Maternal forms have accumulated a lower essential oil content: Cr.13 (2.508%); Fr.5 (2.600%); Fr.1 (2.978%) and Fr.8 (3.435% dry matter). From the group of hybrids studied in the 5th year of vegetation (2021), six genotypes accumulated an essential oil content higher than 5% due to the favorable climatic conditions, which contributed to the synthesis and accumulation of the essential oil.

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Key words: *L. angustifolia*, hybrid, quantitative traits, climatic conditions.

LEUCOJUM AESTIVUM (AMARYLLIDACEAE) – NEW SPECIES FOR THE LOWER PRUT FLORA

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The humid zone of the Lower Prut Lakes Ramsar site is represented by typical plant communities of the floodplain, the preservation of which was facilitated by the strict regime of the border zone maintained in previous decades. The main types of vegetation are azonal communities: floodplain forests, which occupy most of its area, and lowland meadows, located in narrow fragments among trees and shrubs.

On the territory of the forest stand, in places prone to prolonged flooding, forests dominated by *Salix alba* and are most often represented by communities of *Salicetum rubosum*, in which an admixture of *Populus alba*, *Ulmus laevis* and some others. It is also characterized by an unstable moisture regime, weak density and few types of grass cover. The unevenly developed shrub layer contains: *Swida sanguinea*, *Frangula alnus*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Rhamnus cathartica*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Euonymus europaea*, *E. verrucosa*. In the grass cover, *Rubus caesius* is among the most widespread species, growing abundantly in places; *Anthriscus sylvestris*, *Potentilla reptans*, *Phragmites australis*, *Ranunculus repens*, *Galium aparine*, *Poa pratensis*, as well as *Poa palustris*, *Aegopodium podagraria*, *Glechoma hederacea*, *Lysimachia nummularia*, *Symphytum tauricum*, *Myosoton aquaticum*, *Humulus lupulus*, *Equisetum arvense* are more common than others. On wet depressions under the canopy, there are spots of a rare, new for the territory species – *Leucojum aestivum* L., belonging to Amaryllidaceae family. *Leucojum aestivum* is a perennial, bulbous plant. Blooms in April-May and fructifies in June-July. Propagates by seeds and bulbs. The species is decorative and medicinal.

This Critically endangered in the Republic of Moldova vascular plant was registered in April 2022 in the outskirts of Crihana Veche village, Cahul district. The exact location of the population is – west of the village: N 45° 50' 09", E 28° 07' 42". The population covers approximately 50 m², average number of vegetative specimens is 5-8 and flowering plants are 1-2 per square meter.

This finding is new for the territory of the republic, whilst so far two locations are known: in the valley of the Prut river in the vicinity of the commune of Cioara (Hîncești district) and village Sărata-Răzeși (Leova distr.). The species is located at the north-eastern limit of its spreading area. Outside the country it is met in the Mediterranean region, the Caucasus, the Atlantic and Central and south-eastern Europe.

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Key words: *Leucojum aestivum*, floodplain, population, preservation, medicinal specie.

REINTRODUCTION OF *CRAMBE TATARIA* IN THE „LOWER PRUT LAKES” RAMSAR SITE

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Spontaneous vascular plants in Republic of Moldova are under threat with significant loss of plant species and habitat taking place. Local and regional activities on reintroduction of rare and threatened vascular plants in our republic has been started in recent years. The repopulation programs in natural habitats of threatened with extinction species of Community interest and included in international conventions, a rare species in the republic – *Crambe tataria* Sebeók (Brassicaceae), was chosen as one of the objects for study, reproduction and repatriation to nature.

This species, in the region, is protected by the state (category II – endangered), included in the 3rd edition of the Red Data Book of the Republic of Moldova as threatened species (category EN). Internationally protected by the Berne Convention and included in Appendices II and IV of the Habitats Directive. The species is also rare on the territory of Ukraine, where it is included in the Red Book as a vulnerable species.

Crambe tataria is a typical steppe species with a Pontic-Pannonian-Sarmatian disjointed range of distribution. In the Republic of Moldova, it occurs sporadically, except in the north-eastern and southern parts. It grows as part of the grasslands of anthropogenic variants of primary steppes, steppe and limestone slopes, glades and edges of the *Quercus pubescens* forest stands. In order to make available *ex situ* collection of *Crambe tataria* and possible for population recovery and restoration programme into natural habitats, during 2020-21 numerous areas with steppe vegetation were examined, among which we chose „Slobozia Mare – Văleni” natural steppe area.

In June 2021 a number of 15 plantlets obtained from seeds (originally collected from Bugeac steppe plants in August 2020), were planted in the sector of grassland of the *62C0 (Ponto-Sarmatic steppes) habitat. This habitat is one of the most species-rich plants communities in Europe in terms of the plant species. The location of the sector is: N 45° 35' 30", E 28° 09' 48". The surface area represents a steppic slope of western exposition with steepness of circa 30°. The plant community is *Festucetum (valesiaca) – stipeto (ucrainica + lessingiana + capillata) herbosum*, with various herbaceous vascular plants: *Thymus marschallianus*, *Salvia nutans*, *Eryngium campestre*, *Salvia nemorosa*, *Euphorbia cyparissias*, *Poa angustifolia*, *Artemisia austriaca*, *Linum austriacum*, etc.

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Key words: *Crambe tataria*, threatened specie, *ex situ* collection, plantation.

**ASSESSMENT OF THE MORPHOGENETIC AND REGENERATIVE
POTENTIAL OF TRITICALE GENOTYPES
IN *IN VITRO* CULTURE**

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The main focus of research is determined by the country's current and future need for food security. The global and regional climate, energy and food crises pose great challenges to the scientific society, especially to plant genetics and physiology, to obtain new fundamental and applied knowledge in highlighting, evaluating and directing the genetic-physiological mechanisms of the production process and ecological resistance of plants, in this case triticale, by improving adaptability to adverse climatic conditions: increasing resistance to water and heat stress and obtaining healthy yields. In recent decades, thanks to genetic advances in breeding, new varieties have been developed that are much more competitive than current cereal genotypes. These varieties are better because of their high yield capacity and useful agronomic characteristics (fall resistance, resistance to unfavourable environmental conditions, grain filling, etc.). From a technical point of view, triticale has a great capacity to adapt to the most diverse climatic conditions, which gives it undeniable advantages over other cultures that are more susceptible to natural factors. The importance of triticale to the economy is explained by the chemical composition of the grain, which gives it special properties for use in food, animal feed and industry.

The development of theory and new effective methods for plant breeding requires a deep understanding of the mechanisms that determine the spectrum of variability in genetic information. Biotechnological methods, through the application of *in vitro* culture techniques, are a reliable way to obtain pathogen-free biological material, the preservation of genetic resources and the fastest way to create and multiply genotypes. In view of these aspects, we proposed to establish methods of culture that would ensure the successful *in vitro* regeneration of agronomically valuable genotypes.

The biological material used in this study was represented by 3 genotypes of triticale: Ingen 35, Ingen 93, 188TR5021. Mature embryos including 120 embryos from each genotype were used as source material. The basic nutrient substrate was Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium modified and supplemented with L-asparagine, mesoinositol, glycine, sucrose and growth regulators: 2,4-D dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, naphthylacetic acid (NAA) and Kinetin (K), thidiazuron, BAP (6-benzylaminopurine), agar, pH 5.8.

In order to investigate callusogenesis processes, callus cultures were initiated from mature embryos in all genotypes studied. Intense differentiation of explants and the appearance of callus formation on culturing media were observed on day 4, which is in agreement with literature data. Massive callus formation was observed at day 7-8. It was found that, all genotypes tested have a fairly high capacity to induce callus. The frequency of callusogenesis varied from 80.19% (188 TR5027), 92.02% (Ingen 93 standard) and 98.45% (Ingen 35) depending on the genotype. Two types of callus formation were observed. The first type of callus is embryogenic - compact, structured, yellowish colour; the second - non-embryogenic, watery, white-yellowish colour. Despite

evidence in the literature that a non-embryogenic callus is formed first, which either remains the primary callus during culture or is transformed into an embryogenic type, we observed that the non-embryogenic callus did not form meristematic foci throughout explant culture, and no somatic embryogenesis was observed.

The frequency of morphogenesis depends on the induction of embryogenesis and rhizogenesis. Genotypes Ingen 35 and 188 TR5027 formed embryogenic callus at a rate of 34.22% - 40.15%. A low morphogenetic potential is attested by genotype Ingen 93 - 29.24%. Obviously, this is due to the peculiarities of morphogenesis, which is carried out by the organogenesis pathway, with a predominance of the rhizogenous type.

The frequency of rhizogenesis compared to embryogenesis was found to be high with an average of 57.35%. Only in 34.53% of morphogenic callus, the development was embryogenic. This denotes that, the achievement of morphogenesis is determined by the genetic and physiological characteristics of the explant.

Stable plant regeneration is a prerequisite for the practical use of *in vitro* culture. The regeneration frequency averaged 35.07%. Regeneration potential varied significantly by genotype. If for genotypes Ingen 35 (49.03%) and Ingen 93 (40.70%) then for genotype 188 TR5027 it was only 15.50%, a low regeneration rate. The number of regenerants obtained from morphogenic callus was 0.2 and 1.3 pcs per callus. This is due to the fact that a large number of morphogenic callus developed by the rhizogenesis pathway, which precludes the possibility of obtaining plants.

Analysis of variance made it possible to identify significant factors influencing callusogenesis, morphogenesis and regeneration. The frequency of callusogenesis usually depends on a number of random factors. One significant factor for this indicator is genotype. Comparing the contribution of different factors and their interaction with each other, it should be noted that genotype plays a significant role not only in the process of callusogenesis, constituting 76.04%, but also determines regeneration capacity, showing an influence power of 69.15% with significant differences for $P < 0.05$.

Acknowledgments: The study was performed in the framework of the project 20.80009.5107.03 "Efficient valorization of plant genetic resources and advanced biotechnologies to increase the adaptability of crop plants to climate change".

Key words: triticale, varieties, agronomic characteristics, callusogenesis, regeneration, *in vitro* cultures.

GENETIC DIFFERENTIATION AND RELATIONSHIPS OF *OROBANCHE CUMANA* POPULATIONS FROM DIFFERENT SUNFLOWER PRODUCING COUNTRIES

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Orobanche cumana Wallr. is an important species of obligate parasitic weed, naturally distributed from central Asia to south-eastern Europe, where it parasitizes wild *Asteraceae*. Until now, broomrape was recorded in more than 60 countries around the world, causing significant economic damage in crop production especially in Central and Eastern Europe, Spain, Turkey, Israel, Iran, Kazakhstan, and China.

Accelerating rate of parasite evolution and distribution could rapidly diminish the effectiveness of control measures and strategies related to the deployment of resistance genes. Therefore, knowledge about the population structure of parasite are critical to the design of appropriate resistance breeding programs and effective weed control.

Thus, the present study focused on the assessment of the genetic diversity among and within 33 broomrape populations belonging to different sunflower producing countries (Moldova, Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia, China, Turkey) and races (E, G, H) employing microsatellite molecular markers (SSR). The structure of populations was analyzed using different methods (AMOVA, Nei statistics, PCA), based on GenAEx 6.503 and XLSTAT 2014.5.03 software.

The genetic differentiation (Φ_{ST}) between pairs of *O. cumana* populations with different origins indicate values between 0.170 and 0.686 ($p < 0.001$), revealing a strong and very strong differentiation between the populations from different countries. The highest differences were found between populations from China and other countries, indicating that geographic distance is a substantial barrier to gene exchange between populations. AMOVA analysis showed significant genetic differences between groups (countries), as well as between populations within groups and individuals within populations. So, 36% of total genetic diversity was attributable to divergence between groups, 30% to population differentiation within groups and 34% to individual differences within populations. The first 2 components from a PCA explained about 41% of the total variation in the data. Cluster analysis showed that the majority of populations from the Republic of Moldova, Romania and Bulgaria, which are geographically close, were included in one group, Serbian populations formed a separate subcluster, and populations from Turkey and China grouped together. As a result, new data of broomrape population structure were accumulated.

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Key words: *Orobanche cumana* Wallr., genetic diversity, molecular markers SSR, races, population genetic structure.

VARIABILITY OF QUANTITATIVE TRAITS OF CORN HYBRIDS AND INBRED LINES UNDER DROUGHT AND SALINITY

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The variability of the quantitative characters studied at the initial stages of plant development under stressful conditions in hybrids mostly depended on the factor "genotype" ($\eta^2 = 73.44\%$ *** - 88.92% *** (salinity) and 51% ** - 82.9% ** (drought). The hybrids were characterized by higher values of dependence from the "genotype" factor than inbred lines. Lines A285, P346 and hybrids (with maternal genotypes - combinations of lines A285, N6, W23) proved to be the most resistant. The variability of the characters "seedling length" (LP), "root length" (LR) at the stage of immature embryos depended significantly from the factor "genotype" (inbred lines were characterized by higher values than the hybrid combinations). In hybrids the significant dependence of the variability of productivity traits on the "genotype" factor ($\eta^2 = 39.7\%$ *** - 60.94% ***) were found out and the highest values of these traits were recorded in hybrid combinations with maternal genotypes A285xRf7 and A285xW23. Inbred lines were characterized by the highest value of the dependence of the character "diameter of the pollen grain" from the factor "genotype" ($\eta^2 = 39.84\%$ ***), but hybrids had the highest value of the dependence from the factor "abiotic stress" ($\eta^2 = 27.7\%$ ***). The complex evaluation (at diploid and haploid level) of the variability of quantitative characters at different stages of ontogenesis (under osmotic and saline stresses) allowed the highlighting of lines (A285, P346) and hybrids (maternal genotypes A285xN6, A285xW23) with increased resistance. These genotypes can be used in selection schemes to obtain heterotic and productive hybrids. It should be noted that lines L1866, L276, W23, N6, P165, Rf7 can be used as parental genotypes in hybrid combinations with stress resistance.

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Key words: corn, hybrids, variability, quantitative traits, drought, salinity.

**GENOTYPES OF *SALVIA SCLAREA* ESTABLISHMENT
OF ESSENTIAL OIL**

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Special attention has recently been paid to the species *Salvia sclarea* L., due to the multiple uses of the essential oil, which is contained in inflorescences and is used in medicine, the perfumery industry, the brewing industry, etc. At the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection, a series of amelioration researches are carried out, by genetic methods, in order to create new genotypes, which would synthesize and accumulate the highest possible content of high quality essential oil.

The aim of the research is to evaluate and select hybrids of *Salvia sclarea* L., with high and very high content of essential oil.

The biological material used is represented by 84 F₁-F₂ of different types of *Salvia sclarea* L., in the second year of vegetation.

Phenological, biomorphological evaluations were performed according to the methods in force. The essential oil content was determined by hidrodistillation in Ginsberg apparatus.

Research has shown that the hybrids created, evaluated, are resistant to sect, frost, wintering and disease. They are valuable through a string, which ensures increased productivity and high essential oil content. In extreme conditions, the genotypes of *Salvia sclarea* have developed plants with a height of over 91 cm, in some hybrids reaching up to 133.2 cm. Large inflorescences, 42-72 cm long. The number of first-degree branches of the inflorescence ranged from 12.0 to 18.4. Second-degree ramifications - ranged from 18.0 to 44.4 at different genotypes. All these characters facilitated the synthesis and accumulation of a fairly large amount of essential oil. The determination of the essential oil content in the inflorescences, recalculated to dry matter, showed that some hybrids due to drought synthesized and accumulated a relatively low amount of oil - 0.620-0.800%. We specify that 57% are hybrids with a high essential oil content of over 1.0%, and 21.4% are hybrid genotypes with a very high content of essential oil 1,301-1,906% (dry matter).

As a result of the evaluations, 18 exceptional hybrids of the most important character were selected, identified, they synthesize and accumulate 1,301-1,906% (dry matter) essential oil.

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Key words: *Salvia sclarea* L., hybrids, productivity, inflorescence, essential oil content.

**MANIFESTATION OF TRANSGRESSIONS ON THE TRAITS
OF SPIKE PRODUCTIVITY IN F₂ POPULATIONS
OF COMMON WHEAT**

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Transgressive segregation in plant populations is an important factor contributing to the emergence of forms with new characteristics that are superior to the "best" parent. The mechanisms of transgressions have not yet been fully established, but the phenomenon itself is widely used to identify and select plant forms with economically valuable traits that are resistant to pathogens, pests, and unfavorable abiotic factors. Our research is devoted to the study of the influence of the parental forms on the elements of the productivity of the spike of soft winter wheat using the example of 8 F₂ hybrid populations obtained in reciprocal crosses. Positive and negative transgressions were revealed for the traits spike length, number of spikelets per spike, number of grains per spike, weight of one grain, weight of the grains from one spike.

The most significant positive transgressions based on the degree (Tg) and frequency (Tf) were recorded in the case of *the grain mass* character (Tg = 9.32-20.97%; Tf = 31.67-48.33%) in the combinations of wheat Moldova 11 (M11) x Moldova 16 (M66), Moldova 16 (M16) x M11, M16 x Basarabeanca. The combinations Basarabeanca x L M / M3, L M / M3 x Basarabeanca, and of the mass were noted by relatively high indices (Tg = 6.11- 7.50%; Tf = 12.5-25.0%) *grains per spike* - combinations M11 x M16, M16 x M11, Kuialnic x M66, M66 x Kuialnic: Tg = 6.70-15.1%; Tf = 8.33-26.67%. Insignificant positive transgressions were found for the character of *the number of grains per spike* in 5 combinations, and for the number of *spikelets per spike* - only one case (Tg = 4.29%, Tf = 10.83%) in the Kuialnic x M66 combination.

According to the studied traits, genetic distances between parental forms did not affect the manifestation of transgressions. It was found that in F₂ hybrids, obtained on the basis of reciprocal F₁ hybrids, the direction of crossing influenced quite significantly the degree and frequency of transgressions in some combinations, without changing their direction. For example, the combination M16 x M11 recorded for *the mass of a grain* Tg = 11.56%; Tf = 31.67%, and M11 x M16 - Tg = 20.97%; Tf = 35.83%.

This indicates that the successful selection of crossbreeding components and revealed specificity of the manifestation of transgressions in common wheat F₂ hybrids can contribute to the expansion of transgressive variability on the elements of spike productivity in order to create valuable forms.

Key words: common wheat, hybrid, populations, traits productivity.

TRICHODERMA SPECIES FOR PLANTS PROTECTION AGAINST ALTERNARIOIS

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Pathogenic species of *Alternaria* can infect all parts of plants. Worldwide there is an increased presence of *Alternaria spp.* mycotoxins in raw food materials and foods. To reduce their pathogenicity, it is important to use biological methods for plants protection. The aim of the research is to select strains of *Trichoderma* micromycetes for the creation of the microbial control agents against pathogenic species of *Alternaria*.

The research objects presented 20 strains of the *Trichoderma spp* fungi from laboratory's collection. The antagonistic activity of mycelial cultures of *Trichoderma* against the pathogen *A. alternata* was studied by dual culture method. The indicator of inhibition of the pathogen by *Trichoderma spp.* was calculated (%) and assessed (in points) by the degree of overgrowth of the *Alternaria spp* colonies (Поликсенова В.Д., 2004). The antifungal activity of the culture liquid was evaluated by agar diffusion method. (Еропов Н.С., 2004).

On the 10th day of the experiment, two strains; 2N and 13N have given high antagonistic activity with inhibition rates of 94% and 83% respectively. The other *Trichoderma* fungi strains have given less activity with inhibition rates from 59% to 81%. The degree of overgrowth of *Trichoderma spp* fungi of the colony of the pathogen for 9 strains consisted 4 points, 4 strains - 3 points, 5 strains populated the colonies by half - 2 points. The colonization of the pathogen by the *T. virens* strain CNMNEFD-13 was 25% (or 1 point) and there was no growth reduction of the pathogen by the strain 8N (0 points). At the same time, no signs of colonization of the *Trichoderma* culture by the pathogen were seen. Evaluation of the fungicidal activity of the three *Trichoderma spp* liquid cultures was performed by the agar diffusion method. All tested strains have inhibited growth of the pathogen with the formation of the sterile zones with a radius of 13-16 mm.

As a result of the research, two strains of *Trichoderma* fungi, 2N and 13N, from the laboratory's collection, were proposed for further elaboration of the microbial control agents against *Alternaria* fungi.

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Key words: *Trichoderma micromycetes*, microbial agents, mycelial cultures, antifungal activity.

VARIABILITY SOME MORPH-BIOLOGICAL TRAITS IN BREEDING MATERIAL OF CHICKPEA

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This report presents the results of studies of the variability of some morph-biological traits of the intraspecific hybrid combination chickpea ♀Botna (desi, brown seed coat) × ♂Ichel (kabuli, cream seed coat) in the F3 generation. Desi × kabuli crosses have consistently produced high-yielding progenies and have been the source of many new cultivars. Initial steps of breeding programmers are as follows: Creation of genetic variation and selection of genotypes from this bulk.

The research material was 195 individual F3 selections from 20 offspring obtained from the 20 individual selections. The study of the material was carried out in 2021 on the experimental fields of the Institute. With regard to the characteristics of the seeds, it should be noted the formation of intermediate gulabi (or pea shaped) seeds, which accounted for about half of the selections (97). In 13 out of 15 pigmented offspring, seed segregation by pigment (brown/cream colored) was noted, the same number with seed type segregation (desi/gulabi or desi/gulabi/kabuli). In light-seed offspring, segregation is only to the type of seeds and heterogeneity to the size of the seeds.

Seed size (weight of 100 seeds) is a key determinant of genetic variation. In the aspect of the trait, the weight of 100 seeds in this hybrid combination is marked by high variability. The minimum values of the weight of 100 seeds in the progeny A7 (27.36g (25.4 – 29.24) CV=5.1), the only cream/orange-colored seeds. Maximum values in A18 offspring (34.7g (32.6 – 37.9) CV=4.3), all offspring gulabi and brown colored. Minimum variability in A9 offspring ((CV=3.3 (32.8g (31.5-34.6)). Maximum variability in A15(CV=9.1(30.92g (24.1 - 34.7) followed by A4 (CV=8.8 (30.9g (27.4 -37.5)), A10 (CV=8.4 (33.0g (28.4 -38.2) compared to Botna (CV=0.61) and Ichel (CV=0.63) Thus, for the weight of 100 seeds, there is a continuous series of variability, with the presence of positive and negative transgression, Botna var. (28.6 g/100s) and Ichel var. (32.5g/100s).

Plant height variability in progeny is within: CV= 3.7(A9) – CV= 6.5(A15), in variety Botna - CV=2.3. The minimum and maximum plant heights (mean value) are 51.4cm (A7) - 66.8cm (A18), for the Botna variety - 55.7cm, for the Ichel variety - 64.2cm. Ripening obtained offspring within July 30-31 (A7) - August 7-8 (A18). Ripening varieties Botna and Ichel was on August 2 and 6, respectively. Variability of number seeds/plant within CV=17.2 (A18) - CV=31.4(A3) and seeds weight/plant within CV=16.3(A18) - CV=31.1(A3). Maximum value number of seeds (mean) 69.8 and seeds weight /plant 23.5 g (A4).

Key words: hybrid, variability, morphological traits, seeds, chickpea.

ANALYSIS OF MOLECULAR VARIANCE (AMOVA) OF *OROBANCHE CUMANA* POPULATIONS

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The first reports that attest the presence of *Orobanche cumana* Wallr. (broomrape) in sunflower fields date back to 1866 in Russia. Then, due to the expansion of sunflower cultivated area, in 100 years this parasite has spread in Bulgaria, Moldova, Romania, Serbia, Spain, China and in the last 50 years – in the main sunflower producing countries around the world. Until now, eight races of *O. cumana* have been identified, from A to H.

The objective of this research was to study the genetic diversity of 33 *O. cumana* populations originated from 6 countries (Bulgaria, Moldova, Romania, Serbia, China, Turkey) using microsatellite molecular markers like SSR and ISSR. The evaluations were conducted in artificially infected pots in greenhouse conditions. The most highly virulent broomrape races, G and H, was revealed in the majority of studied countries, except of Serbia (race E or less virulent than E). The study of genetic variability of 33 populations was performed based on the analysis of molecular variance method (AMOVA). The results showed for the both marker systems (SSR: within populations 37%, among populations 63%; ISSR: 41% and 59%, respectively), that the most of the total variance was attributed to the differences between populations. At the country level, AMOVA dates for Bulgarian broomrape populations also presented a higher variability among populations while for the populations from Moldova, Serbia, China and Turkey, the molecular variations within populations were a major source of genetic variation. AMOVA results showed that both marker sets, based on molecular data SSR and ISSR, keep the same tendency of distribution of genetic variations.

The molecular differences between identified broomrape races (\leq E, G, H) very little contributed to the total variability (SSR: among races 10%; ISSR: 11%, respectively). According to the SSR markers (separately for three groups of races) genetic variations within populations are higher for the broomrape populations race H (53%) and lower for those from race G (30%) and \leq E (36%). In the case of ISSR markers, molecular variations were almost equally divided between intra- and interpopulation diversity, with predominance of diversity between populations for all groups.

In this context, our results indicate that *O. cumana* specie has a very great genetic potential and a high degree of genetic variations which can determine the evolution of more virulent races which is important for creating some sunflower crop breeding strategies and their control.

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Key words: *Orobanche cumana* Wallr., AMOVA, populations, races, genetic diversity.

ADAPTIVE CAPACITY OF THE *FAGUS SYLVATICA* L. POPULATION FROM THE SLOVAK REPUBLIC

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The European beech *Fagus sylvatica* L. is one of the most important tree species not only in the Republic of Moldova, but throughout the European continent, both economically and ecologically. Beech forests in the Republic of Moldova need to be restored with populations that are resistant to globally changing climatic conditions. In this investigation, we studied the possibility of increasing the natural adaptive potential of beech population from the Slovak Republic, Nitra region, Topoľčianky, through the use of plant growth bioregulators capsicoside and genistifolioside at a concentration of 0.001%. The gibberellic acid was used as standard regulator of plant growth. Seeds were stratified at a temperature of $+4\pm 2$ °C. After the germination, they were sown in solarium with drip irrigation, but without regulation of the air temperature, which in summer rose above $+35$ °C, sometimes reaching $+55$ °C. The viability of *Fagus sylvatica* seeds collected in autumn 2019 averaged 65.6%. Treatment of seeds with solutions of capsicoside and genistifolioside before germination leads to stimulation of daily seed germination by 18.5-22.2% and to significant reduction in the period of total seed germination by 20-22 days. As a result, $87.01\pm 0.03\%$ of seeds germinated in the experiment with bioregulators, which was significantly higher than in the control and standard. The adaptation of germinated seeds to solarium conditions after treatment with bioregulators was 2.5-2.9 times higher than in the standard and 3.0-3.3 times higher than in the control. The survival of seedlings in experimental variants at supraoptimal temperatures was on average 2.7-3.0 times higher than in the standard and control. Beech seedlings treated with bioregulators had the leaves with significantly bigger leaf surface area, the leaves were larger by 2.3 ± 0.7 cm and wider by 0.8 ± 0.4 cm that contributed to the greatest photosynthetic process. The relative chlorophyll index in the phase of three pairs of true leaves of seedlings in the variants capsicoside and genistifolioside 0.001% was 144.9 ± 3.5 and 145.6 ± 3.7 g/m², respectively, which significantly exceeded the control (135.7 ± 3.2 g/m²) and the variant with gibberellic acid (121.5 ± 2.9 g/m²). Two-year-old seedlings were transferred from the solarium to natural conditions, in mixt hornbeam/beech forest of the "Plaiul Fagului" Scientific Reservation. The use of plant growth bioregulators led to a high degree of adaptability of seedlings, 90.17% of transferred plants survived.

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Key words: *Fagus sylvatica* L., adaptive potential, germination, viability of seeds, bioregulators

**EVALUATION, ESTIMATION AND MONITORING
DIABROTICA VIRGIFERA VIRGIFERA LE CONTE**

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In the Republic of Moldova, corn (*Zea mays*) is one of the most important cereal crops for the food industry and feed reserves. Annually, this crop occupies an area of over 270.0 thousand ha, which constitutes approximately the 5th part of the area of arable land. The emergence of one of the most dangerous corn pests, such as the western corn rootworm (*Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* Le Conte) DVV, which has already managed to spread throughout the country, creates a real danger to corn production and the country's economy in general. Although, in the countries of the European Union, DVV was considered a harmful organism, regulated with a state of quarantine, but its spread could not be prevented. A number of recommendations have been developed based on the application of crop rotation, adequate monitoring of pest populations and other relevant measures to prevent the spread of harmful organisms and control measures.

Traps with synthetic sex pheromone have proven to be an effective tool for both monitoring the pest population (accumulating specimens for study) and a total control method, such as sterilization and mass capture.

The active component of the sex pheromone of DVV *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* Le Conte, it is 1,7-dimethylnonyl propanoate. The optimization of the synthesis scheme, the obtaining of the high purity substance as well as its analysis, is important and necessary.

Subsequently, the synthesized substance was impregnated on synthetic rubber septa with a dose of: 1 mg per dispenser. DVV synthetic sex pheromone dispensers were fixed on the "open-type" trap - a piece of laminated cardboard with entomological glue and then attached directly to the plant, in the corn field, with a distance of about 20m between them and further verification were made 1 -3 times a week. As usual, the first catches of the imago phase of the pest were recorded in the second half of June. The peak of the pest's flight falls in mid-July, with a considerable decrease in the number of pests caught by mid-August.

The economic damage threshold is 5,5 imago per plant. In the northern part of the country, in the village of Ocnița, the village of Girbova, the pest exceeded 7 times the economic threshold of damage, which is explained by the relief shape of the field, the rotation of crops and the location of the corn field compared to others. Pests have been recorded in technical corn and seed fields, where the principle of monoculture is followed. The effectiveness of protection measures is hampered by high pest migration capacity and an effective control scheme.

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Key words: *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*, crop rotation, corn production, 7-dimethylnonyl propanoate, economic damage.

THE DEVELOPMENT OF VITICULTURE THROUGH THE REQUIREMENTS PRISM OF GREEN ECONOMY

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The primary imperative of the sustainable development of the wine sector is to obtain high production, with low consumption of resources, in conditions of increased economic efficiency and the use of technological links that contribute to reducing energy consumption. High quality wine derivatives can be ensured, if three main factors are taken into account: the genotype (variety), location of the plantation (soil and climatic conditions) and applied technology (cultivation and processing).

The intraspecific genotypes have a wide capacity for use, but at the same time do not ensure the overcoming of climate change barrier. That is why, taking into account the functionality of genotypes and the use of technical algorithms and interspecific hybridization methods, more plastic rhizogenic interspecific genotypes should be created in terms of their adaptation to climate change, with beneficial repercussions on the sustainable development of the wine sector. As a result of crossing *V. vinifera* L. with *M. rotundifolia* Michx. were obtained and identified interspecific vine genotypes that allow the expansion of the vine cultivation area to the northern areas, while reducing the number of chemical treatments, which will contribute to obtaining ecological products and will improve environmental protection. The rhizogenic interspecific genotypes have an early period of grape ripening, can be multiplied by cuttings, without grafting, thus obtaining rhizogenic propagating material that contributes to reducing the costs of setting up vineyards.

They were approved as table grape varieties like: "Malena", "Nistreana" and "Algumax" and grape varieties for fresh consumption and processing: "Augustina", "Alexandrina" and "Amethyst". By creating plantations, will contribute to the extension of the area to the northern limit of vine cultivation.

Key words: area, genotype, green economy, viticulture.

MOLECULAR ASSESSMENT OF *F. GRAMINEARUM* IN SEVERAL MOLDAVIAN MAIZE GENOTYPES

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Fusarium graminearum is a typical pathogen of many cereal crops, causing grain, stalk and seedling rots. In maize, this pathogen causes Gibberella ear blight and is able to infect kernels through the stigma. Optimal conditions for the development of the fungus include moderate temperatures around 25°C and high humidity, and the species is distributed throughout the maize cultivation region. It has been established that some strains of *F. graminearum* can synthesize DON mycotoxin, which is highly toxic and provokes alimentary-toxic aleukia. Non-compliance with the rules of corn agrotechnology, in particular, non-compliance with crop rotation, insufficient tillage, too high planting density, irrational use of fertilizers and pesticides can induce DON synthesis in toxigenic *F. graminearum* strains.

Molecular diagnostics of toxigenic strains of *F. graminearum* was carried out in kernel samples of several local maize genotypes grown under field conditions in the Republic of Moldova. The fungus was identified using the nested-PCR method with primer pairs based on the *F. graminearum* genomic cluster of the fungus involved in DON synthesis (*Fusarium graminearum* isolate 23-4 Tri core gene cluster, complete sequence). External pair: ftri8gr1 (forward) - CTCCGGTAATGTTTCTCGTCACT, ftri8gr4 (reverse) - CGCTGCTGAGGGTTTTACCAT. Internal pair: fqtri8gr2 (forward) - CTCGTCACCTCCTTGATGACACA, fqtri8gr3 (reverse) - GGGGGCCGACATTCACCTTC. Comparison of the frequency of infection of the studied samples with the control genotype B73 was carried out using the Student's test for two independent samples ($p < .05$).

In 2020, there was a decrease in the frequency of infection by the fungus for all genotypes, which was due to high temperatures and low rainfall in the spring-summer period. On the contrary, in 2021, which was characterized by moderate temperatures, high air humidity and heavy rainfall during the period from April to July, an increase in the infection rate of *F. graminearum* in corn kernels was observed. The highest mean frequency of infection was noted for kernels of the CP137 and CP148 genotypes. At the same time, KU123 and MK01 genotypes showed the lowest frequency of infection with *F. graminearum*; the average infection frequency during the observation period did not exceed 30%. A statistically significant lower infection frequency was observed for genotypes KU123 ($t=2.38$, $p=.02$) and MK01 ($t=2.84$, $p=.01$), while for CP137 and CP148 there was no significant difference in the frequency of *F. graminearum* in comparison with the susceptible line B73. Thus, the locally bred genotypes MK01 and KU123 are of interest for breeding programs aimed at obtaining maize lines and varieties with increased resistance to *F. graminearum*.

Key words: *Fusarium graminearum*, genotype, pathogen, nested-PCR, frequency of infection.

ASSESSMENT OF GERmplasm DIVERSITY USED IN THE MAIZE INBRED LINES DEVELOPMENT

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Diversity of germplasm sources is the raw material for breeding programs to permanently improving of agronomic performance and reduce plant vulnerability to various pathogens and pests. In hybrid maize breeding, information on germplasm genetic diversity and heterotic groups is very useful in inbred line development and planning crosses for hybrid cultivar development.

The purpose of present investigation was to estimate the phenotypic and genetic diversity of 10 maize inbred lines from the main germplasm groups, which are currently used in maize breeding programs. Phenotypic diversity was estimated by determining the phenotypic diversity index (*idf*), calculated based on 28 quantitative and qualitative characters. Genetic diversity was assessed by the mid-parent heterosis (H, %) and SCA constants (\hat{s}_{ij}) for grain yield.

The high level of phenotypic similarities, confirmed by the low values of the *idf* index were noticed between the A654 and Co125 inbred lines (*idf* = 5.2), W153R and MK390 lines (*idf* = 5.3); Co125 and F2 lines (*idf* = 5.7), MK01 and A632 inbreds (*idf* = 5.9). Among the other inbred lines, a high level of diversity was attested (*idf* > 7.0).

The high values of reproductive heterosis (H = 57.6-182.6%) noted in the crosses between inbred lines of different origin, were demonstrated their high diversity at the genetic level and confirm their different genealogical origin. The most accentuated genetic similarity was noted between the A632 and MK390 inbred lines (H = 57.6%), being demonstrated the affiliation of the MK390 line to the BSSS germplasm group. The high values of heterosis, observed in all crosses obtained with the F2, CM7 and MO17 inbreds reveal their significant differences from the other genotypes used in the study, which confirms their belonging to distinct sources of germplasm. A high degree of similarity at the non-additive gene interactions level was attested between the CO125 and P502 lines ($\hat{s}_{ij} = -0.34$ t / ha), A632 and MK390 inbreds ($\hat{s}_{ij} = -0.31$). Significant positive values of SCA constants recorded at all crosses made with Mo17 and F2 inbred lines were confirmed their genetic distance from other genotypes.

The generalized results regarding the diversity assessment methods highlighted the essential phenotypic and genetic differences of the Mo17, F2 and CM 7 inbred lines compared to the other genotypes. Therefore, these lines represent distinct groups of germplasm. Thus, the data allow the classification of the studied inbred lines in the following global germplasm groups: Lacaune (line F2), Lancaster (MO17), Iodent (MK01), Reid (A632, A654, BC27D4, CO125, P502, MK390) and Ottawa Flint (CM7 line).

These results will be useful in the systematisation, management and more efficient use of initial material in maize breeding programs for new inbred lines and high yielding maize hybrids development.

Key words: maize, genetic diversity, germplasm, phenotypic diversity, heterosis.

**BIOLOGICAL EFFICACY OF THE NEEM OIL
FOR THE CONTROL OF *APHIS GOSSYPHII***

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The role of insecticides in human society is very important. Phytophagous insects can cause losses of 10 to 90% of cultivated crops. In addition to affecting crop growth, harmful organisms can subsequently damage stored crops. However, using of synthetic pesticides has a direct negative effect on human and animal health. Also, the excessive or inappropriate use of synthetic insecticides causes biodiversity loss and occurrence of pests' resistance to these substances. The use of secondary metabolites synthesized by some plant species as part of their natural self-defense against pathogens and pests seems to be an excellent alternative to synthetic insecticides.

In our study which took place during the 2021 year we tested the biological efficacy of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) seed oil on *Aphis gossypii* populations. The treatment was performed under laboratory and greenhouse conditions using cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L) plants. Regarding the laboratory research the cucumber seedlings were planted in a greenhouse and infected with aphid populations transferred from a natural agroecosystem. Samples were collected from cucumber leaves in the greenhouse. The leaf blades inhabited by pests were placed in Petri dishes in 4 variants and 4 replicas for each variant. Counting of dead individuals was performed next day after treating the samples with extracts working solutions. The solutions were prepared in 0% (control), 0.1% and 0.5% neem oil concentrations while 1% ecological Pelecol insecticide was used as a standard. In the greenhouse experiments the aphids inhabited cucumber plants naturally. The plants were also treated with four variants (each variant in three repetitions): experimental variants - neem oil in two doses (8 Litre per Hectare (L/ha) and 10 L/ha), standard (Pelecol EO – 10 L/ha) and control.

The laboratory experiments showed strong aphicide effects (especially the highest concentration variant) the pests dying before they could leave the treated cucumber leaves. The greenhouse studies confirmed the potent insecticide action and they showed also a moderate repellent effect. The extract inhibited aphid feeding for a period of 5-7 days but was not able to completely inhibit the consumption of plants. The neem oil in a dose of 10 L/ha recorded highest biological efficiency - 90.05% (this was slightly higher than Pelecol result - 89.09%) and has the potential to be used as an aphicide.

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Key words: *Azadirachta indica*, *Aphis gossypii*, harmful organisms, oil, repellent effect, treatment.

PHENOTYPICAL VARIABILITY OF FETAL TRAITS IN MUTANT TOMATO FORMS

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When creating new varieties and hybrids of tomato, the fundamental role is given to the characteristics of the fruit, since it is on them that the volume and quality of the final product, which determine the price of the efforts invested by the breeder, depend.

The main characteristics of the fetus include color, shape, weight and thickness of the pericarp. Knowing the degree of their variability depending on the genotypic features of the mutant forms and environmental conditions will make it possible to use them more effectively as a new germ plasm.

Of the many traits of the fetus, the main one is its mass. This is a complex trait, determined by a large number of genes that cause its significant variation. This opinion is confirmed by our results. The average coefficient of variation in fetal weight in the studied mutants (125 forms) was 33.6%, which characterizes the trait as highly variable. The highest amplitude of trait variability (from 20.7% to 66.4%) was found in 45.7% of the studied mutant forms. The average degree of intrapopulation variability (10.2 - 19.8%) was shown by 41.4% of genotypes from the collection of mutants. Only 12.9% of genotypes were characterized by high homeostasis (2.8–9.4%). The variability of the trait "fruit weight" was high both among plants of the population of one mutant form and between fruits within the same plant. In large-fruited mutant forms with round and flat-round fruits, the variability was higher (29.7%) than in forms with oval and plum-shaped (17.8%).

Despite the revealed high degree of variability of the trait "fetal weight" in the studied mutant forms, it should be noted that the genetic features of the trait, determined by the norm of reaction to environmental conditions specific for each genotype, are preserved. A high heterogeneity of the mutant collection in terms of fruit color was revealed, which is represented by a large number of mutant genes: *o at*, *ep*, *gs*, *gf*, *hp*, *t*, *u*, *ug*, *lp*, *l*, *r*, *sh*, *y*, which determine the nature and intensity of fruit color. The content of *lycopene* and *β -carotene* in fruits is controlled by genes *B*, *B^c*, *B^{og}*, *Del*. The *pat* and *pat-2* genes give the fruits fleshiness and high elasticity. The degree of pubescence of different parts of the plant, including fruits, is determined by the *Ln*, *p*, *vi*, and *Wo^m* genes. The presence of keeping quality genes (*rin*, *nor* and *alc*) ensures the preservation of fruits up to 2-3 months. The severity of these signs varies greatly depending on the growing conditions of plants.

Knowledge of the nature of manifestation and the degree of variability of the declared traits presupposes their successful use in breeding to improve existing and create new varieties and hybrids of F₁ tomato.

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Key words: fetal weight, fruit weight, mutant forms variability, tomato.

USING MUTANT *ls* AND *br* GENES OF TOMATO TO CREATE A NEW SOURCE MATERIAL

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It is known that when mutant forms are crossed with other biotypes, there is an exchange and enrichment of the population with genetic material. Some mutant genes in the process of splitting activate the reactions of genetic recombination's and, thereby, expand the range and level of intrapopulation variability available for selection in $F_2 - F_3$, making it possible to obtain new valuable source material and thereby increase the efficiency of the breeding process.

To create new forms of tomato with limited formation of lateral shoots and short internodes, two genotypes were involved in the breeding process, the semimutant line 11069 and the mutant sample Mo 443, which are carriers of the *br* (*brachytic*) and *ls* (*lateral suppressor*) mutant genes that control these traits. Using these forms, and cultural lines – L28, L111, L187, L828, L556, as well as highly productive, large-fruited varieties – MilOranj, MaKrista, Fasel, with a set of valuable quantitative and qualitative traits that have genes – *sp+*, *sp±*, *sp*, *ssp*, *u*, *nor*, *rin*, *ex*, *j-2*, 8 hybrid combinations were created.

The analysis of F_1 hybrids revealed 100% dominance of the shoot-forming ability of cultivated parental forms in all the studied combinations. The number and size of lateral shoots was different and was in direct proportion to the degree of their development in parental forms. The trait “length of internodes” was inherited according to an intermediate type (mid-parent).

In the splitting F_2 populations of all hybrid combinations involving the mutant forms L11069 and Mo 443, there are very few plants with the absence or single lateral shoots (7.3 - 12.7%), they have short internodes (< 6 cm), but at the same time a large part of the flowers (from 41 to 100%) on the inflorescences of these plants with deformations of varying severity. It has been established that the less lateral shoots are formed and the shorter the internodes on the plant, the more morphological deviations in the structure of flowers and the smaller the fruits. This indicates a multiple pleiotropic effect from the influence of the *ls* and *br* genes due to their insufficient cultivation, or these side effects are due to linkage with other genes that have an indirect effect, enhancing the nature of the manifestation of mutant traits.

From different hybrid combinations, genotypes with a smaller number of lateral shoots, reduced internodes, and a normally developed reproductive system were isolated to study their offspring in the $F_3 - F_4$ generations.

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Key words: mutant forms, tomato, breeding process, F_1 hybrids, *br* (*brachytic*) gene, *ls* (*lateral suppressor*) gene.

EVALUATION OF ROS ACCUMULATION IN TOMATO ROOTS DURING POSTSTRESS ACLIMATIZATION

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Reactive oxygen species (ROS) fluctuations in time and space can be interpreted as signals to regulate growth, development, cell death and stress responses. The microscopic analysis obtained on 4 tomato genotypes (*S. pimpinellifolium*, Rufina, Mihaela and Mary Gratefully) show that the length of the ROS area accumulations in the root apical meristem decreases significantly in development dynamics - 96, 120 and 144 hours after seed immersion in water and 24, 48, 72 hours poststress (hps). The values of the ROS area length in optimal conditions, 96 hours, varied between 42.5 μm (Mary Gratefully) and 30.4 μm (*S. pimpinellifolium*) and for 144 hours decrease down to 22,4 and 2,4 μm , respectively. The heat stress determined a significant decrease of 2-15 times the length of ROS area compared to the control at 24 hps. The same trend for all analyzed terms within the genotype was maintaining except for *S. pimpinellifolium*, in which the length of ROS area increased at 48 and 72 hps, comparing to 24 hps variant. In the case of drought stress, accumulation of ROS was attested at 24 hps only, the other terms no positive histochemical response was recorded for ROS. Stress also causes a redistribution of ROS accumulations in all areas root, in a manner specific to the type of stress and genotype. Elongation of the root at 72 hours post-heat stress indicated higher values for the genotypes that marked and higher indices of the area with ROS accumulations in the following order: Mary Gratefully, Rufina, Mihaela and *S. pimpinellifolium*.

The analysis of the variance of ROS area length established a significant contribution of all analyzed factors and their interaction, the highest share of variation being due to *stress* (17%), *hours poststress* (13%), their interaction (11%), and of *genotype* (9%).

Evaluation of root cell viability by Evans Blue test established that germs exposed to heat or drought stress, compared to the optimal variant, microscopically marked penetration of the reagent in almost all meristem area at all evaluation terms -24, 48 and 72 hps. Thus, inhibition of main root growth under stress as result of loss cell integrity in the meristematic zone was accompanied by stimulation of adventitious root growth, which could be marked by ROS accumulations in the tip of adventitious roots, and their location was in the immediate vicinity of the meristematic area compared to their location in the differentiation zone in the optimal conditions. Morphological analyzes established differences in root architecture of plants exposed to heat or drought and optimal conditions according to the length of the main root, the number, length and location of secondary roots. Drought and heat stress applied at the germination stage drastically change the root parameters, which can have repercussions on further plant development.

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Key words: genotype, tomato, reactive oxygen species, heat and drought stress, germination, root.

EXPANSION AND DIVERSITY OF THE BROOMRAPE RACES IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The recent increase in the world production of *Helianthus annuus* L. and the rapid evolution of its parasite - the broomrape (*Orobancha cumana* Wallr.) led to changes in the genetic structure of *O. cumana*. So far, eight races of broomrape (A, B, C, D, E, F, G and H) have been described, which have unfavorable consequences for sunflower cultivation. In the Republic of Moldova, the broomrape was first mentioned in 1863, only about 20 years after the introduction of sunflower in culture. Moreover, in the 1960s, a new biotype, was called the Moldovan race, or C race (Sharova, 1969). In the early 2000s, the results obtained on racial status allowed the reporting of race A-F. It should be noted that race A was predominant, being identified in about 30%. B race was highlighted in 22% of the locations, C race - 18%, D race - 15%, E race - 12%. Compared to the races \leq E, the presence of the race F was identified only in 3% of the localities (Petcovici et al., 2009). Thus, the proposed goal was to assess the racial status of *O. cumana* in the Republic of Moldova, in dynamics during the last 10 years (2010-2020). For this purpose, a series of expeditions were carried out in the country in which more than 130 sunflower fields were evaluated, and it was found that the infection is widespread. Subsequently, in 2014, the investigations covered almost the entire surface of the country (158 fields in 95 localities) (Duca et al., 2017). Broomrape was found in 63% of the southern localities, 47% of the central localities and only in 10% of the analyzed fields in the northern regions. At the same time, *O. cumana* seeds were collected from more than 60 populations, which were used to establish the strains of the parasite using differentiating host plants. As a result, the entire complex of known physiological races was detected. Thus, the less virulent races than E, were predominant, being identified in 37% of the investigated localities, the presence of the F race was noticed in 14% of the localities, especially from the south of the republic, and the G race in 27%. Research has shown that nine of the populations surveyed also infected resistant breeders resistant to the race G, which indicates the identification of the race H for the first time in the Republic of Moldova (22%). The appearance of this biotype of the parasite in our country was confirmed following a new assessment of the racial status of the broomrape, conducted in 2019, on agricultural fields in 15 localities in the Republic of Moldova. The results of this study reported the presence of races E-H, the new *O. cumana* rene spread entirely throughout the country, the race H becoming the dominant physiological races of the parasite (56.2%) (Duca et al., 2022). The results obtained in the present study demonstrate an accelerated evolution of this sunflower parasite on the agricultural fields of the Republic of Moldova. Following the expeditions made in 2014, the presence of the race H of broomrape was reported, which was later shown to have spread over the entire surface of the country.

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Key words: genotype, tomato, reactive oxygen species, heat and drought stress, germination, root.

BIOMORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF SOME SPECIES OF THE GENUS *CUPHEA* IN CONDITIONS OF INTRODUCTION

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Cuphea is a New World genus and the largest of the 32 genera of *Lythraceae* with about 260 species. Economic value of these plants is very diverse but of special interest is the ability of plants to synthesize and store oil (16 to 42%) in seeds containing capric, caprylic, lauric and myristic acids used in production of laundry powders, plasticizers, and also in perfumery, medicine and in production of biodiesel. The purpose of our investigations was to study the manifestation of biological parameters of the representatives of the genus *Cuphea* - *C. lanceolata* (1), *C. viscosissima* (2), *C. lutea* (3), in conditions of their introduction in the Central Area of Moldova. Thus, plants of all genotypes were characterized as herbaceous, annual plants with tap root system and upright stem. They have simple, opposite, and entire-kind leaves. Flowers are small, single, zygomorphic, located interaxillary. Corolla has six unequal petals, they are uniformly violet-cherry colored in plants of the 1st and 2nd species. Plants of the 3rd species have flowers with two violet petals and four white petals with red central vein. Androecium has eleven stamens located in two rings. Gynoecium is syncarpous. Stem, leaves and sepals have sticky hairy surface. Fruit represents a seed case where small oblate brown seeds develop. The investigated species are characterized by a fairly long flowering period (from the second decade of June until the first frosts). Representatives of the first 2 species begin to flower 8-10 days earlier than genotypes of the 3rd species. Fruit formation was noted to begin in the first decade of July and fructification lasted till October. To determine reproductive potential of plants, the analysis of pollen must be conducted because the changes in basic characteristics of pollen influence fertility and reproductive biology of plants. We performed morphological description of pollen grains using scanning electron microscopy method. For characteristics of species, the following parameters were used: diameter, shape, surface and aperture of pollen grain. Pollen grains of the first species have oblate shape, 20.65 to 23.04 μm in diameter. Aperture contains three pores, pore diameter varies within 4.5 to 6.0 μm . Pollen grains are sincolporate and have no apocolpium. The structure is wrinkled in mesocolpium. *Cuphea viscosissima* Jacq. Pollen grains are sincolporate, with three prominent pores and streaks located on the opposite poles. The shape of pollen grains is oblate, 21.0 to 22.86 μm in diameter. Pore diameter varies within 4.0 to 6.0 μm . Mesocolpium surface is smooth except for the area around the pore where it has wrinkled sculpture. *Cuphea lutea* Rose. The shape of pollen grains is oblate, 24.57 to 26.09 μm in diameter. Pore diameter varies within 7.62 to 8.0 μm . Mesocolpium surface is smooth except for the area around the pore where it has wrinkled sculpture. *Cuphea* species investigated show significant potential for productivity and resilience in introductory conditions.

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Key words: genotype, reproductive potential, pollen grain, morphological traits.

**STUDY OF LAKE FUNGI BIODIVERSITY IN FROM THE
LA IZVOR LAKE (CHISINAU MUNICIPALITY)**

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Fungi (mushrooms) are indispensable components of biota in any ecosystem. In aquatic environments, fungi belong to important microbial communities for organic decomposition, nutrient cycle and energy flows and play important roles in the dynamics of the trophic network of freshwater ecosystems. Fungi are among the least studied groups of aquatic microorganisms, so the aim of the research was to study the biodiversity of fungi in Lake Izvor.

247 strains of fungi isolated from samples taken from La Izvor lake (water, silt, and biofilm) were studied. For the isolation of fungi, 5 agar media were used (Czapek: Sabourand, Malt - agar, Agar - nutritious, Raistrik), specific for the growth of filamentous fungi.

The highest fungal biodiversity was detected in the silt samples (87 strains), then in the water samples (85 strains), and the least in the biofilm samples (75 strains).

The cultural and morphological features of the isolated fungal strains were studied. As a result of the research, representatives of 18 genera of fungi were found, these being: *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Trichoderma*, *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Botrytis*, *Monilinia*, *Mucor*, *Rhizopus*, *Acremonium*, *Cladosporium*, *Trichocladium*, *Phoma*, *Chaetomium*, *Stachybotrys*, *Talaromyces*. In all studied samples, the most common genera of filamentous fungi proved to be *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus*, followed by the genera *Trichoderma* and *Alternaria*. Together these genera represent about 90% of the total number of isolated strains. It was found that depending on the place of isolation, the representatives of the genus *Penicillium* predominate in the water, and in the silt, and biofilm samples – the representatives of the genus *Aspergillus*.

The obtained results showed that, from the genus *Penicillium*, the species predominates: *P. verrucosum* and *P. corylophilum*, from the genus *Aspergillus* predominates *A. niger* followed by *A. flavus* and *A. fumigatus*. *Trichoderma* strains belonging to the species were found: *viride*, *harzianum*, *atrobrunneum*, *simmonsii*, *longibrachiatum*, etc. *F. oxysporum* and *F. moniliforme* predominate among the species found in the genus *Fusarium*. Most of the isolated silt strains were *Aspergillus niger* and *Alternaria*.

The data obtained are in accordance with the data in the literature which states that freshwater predominates filamentous fungi of the genera *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria*, which contribute to the breakdown of organic matter, nutrient cycle, and energy flows.

Key words: fungi, biodiversity, La Izvor lake.

NUTRITIONAL QUALITY AND DIGESTIBILITY OF MAIZE HYBRID PLANTS FOR SILAGE

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In order to assess the silage potential of maize hybrids, the nutritional quality and the enzymatic *in vitro* digestibility of five local maize hybrids (ZP 707, ZP 7357, ZP 7072, ZP 7777, and ZP 6263) was tested in the laboratory of the Group for Food Technology and Biochemistry of the Maize Research Institute "Zemun Polje". The hybrids were grown at a total of four locations, one in Srem (Autonomous Province of Vojvodina) and three in Central Serbia. The hybrid 7001 was used as a standard. The selection of hybrids for this research was made on the basis of the actuality of individual hybrids and the market orientation of the Maize Research Institute. The following properties were investigated: dry matter content, lignocellulose fiber content, and *in vitro* dry matter digestibility of the whole plant. According to the achieved results, it can be concluded that hybrids ZP 707, ZP 7357, followed by ZP 7777 proved to be the maize genotypes highly preferable for the production of silage. All tested hybrids achieved better results than the standard in most locations. Hybrid ZP 707 on average had the highest *in vitro* dry matter digestibility ($61.43 \pm 1.86\%$), as well as the lowest content of all lignocellulosic fibers (NDF-52.76%, ADF-24.40%, ADL-2.58, hemicellulose-28.36, and cellulose-21.82%), which all indicates its potential as a silage maize form suitable for cultivation in different agro-ecological conditions. In terms of digestibility and dry matter content, the ZP 707 hybrid can be singled out as the most stable, i.e. it is appropriate for growing both in lowland areas and at higher altitudes. ZP 6263 proved to be the most inferior hybrid at most locations, while based on *in vitro* digestibility and dry matter content, ZP 7072 hybrid varied the most. The digestibility of the whole plant was negatively affected by the higher content of primarily lignin (ADL), followed by ADF and cellulose fraction share. Although it is optimal to harvest silage maize in the waxy maturity stage of grain ripeness, when the dry matter content of the whole plant is in the range between 30 and 35%, the harvest time in some hybrids in some locations was significantly exceeded, which affected the results of dry matter digestibility. The findings obtained in this study can be highly useful for future breeding programs directed toward creating new and improved silage maize hybrids.

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Key words: hybrid, maize, silage potential, lignocellulose, enzymatic *in vitro* digestibility

**IMPORTANCE OF WALNUT (*Juglans regia* L.) WITHIN
REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**

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Among fruit growing species in the Republic of Moldova, the walnut is the most representative and the most appreciated from economic, social, ecological and aesthetical points of view. Always walnut has been a symbol of prodigality, virtue, resistance and wellbeing for Moldovan people. Walnut image is presented in the folk songs, romances, ballads, sayings, riddles, ceremonial customs mentioned in the writings of the local folklorists. It is a secular tradition to plant one walnut tree when a son is born into the family. Peasants always like to plant a walnut tree at the corner of their house - a pleasant place for recreation. Usually respected households have a tall and vigorous tree, which would be able to listen and understand you so well. Thus, it is the spirit of the people of Moldovan lands to grow walnuts. The walnut has multiple uses due primarily to the food value of its fruits, leaves, and due to its quality wood, highly appreciated in the furniture industry, as well as the use of trees in some cases to fix kneaded and degraded land. Aesthetic and ecological role of walnuts is well known in the frame of different kinds of social places (for example: parks, schools, sanatoriums, monasteries). Walnuts are the preferable tree species on secondary roadsides, alleys and usually serve as a basic species in the different kind of alleys and forest belts. Like in other regions dried nuts are gifted to children during religious celebrations. The dried kernel is used in preparing pies, cakes, candies and ice cream as well as simple foods like honey with kernel, etc. A special roly-poly called "*invirtita*" is present at Christmas, Easter and other religious celebrations and commemorations. Nuts kernel is an important ingredient of diverse culinary dishes such as salads, pastes, etc. Green nuts are used to make balsam, "sugariness". Alcoholic extracts from kernels mixed with different medicinal herbs, to vitaminize wines and spirits, which are used in medical scope too. The juvenile fruits are used for the preparation of different special extracts as an antidysentery or intestinal astringent function. Over centuries in our country shelled fresh kernel is eaten during the month of September (when lipids content is minimal), after special religious days, 29 August - Walnut Easter. Excellent edible and technical oil is extracted from walnut kernels, which is usually used also for technical purposes: in painting, to obtain technical ink and in the preparation of numerous cosmetic and pharmaceutical products. Among other fruit growing species in the Republic of Moldova, Green nuts are used to make balsam, "sugariness". Alcoholic extracts from kernels mixed with different medicinal herbs, to vitaminize wines and spirits, which are used in medical scope too. The juvenile fruits are used for the preparation of different special extracts as an antidysentery or intestinal astringent function. Over centuries in our country shelled fresh kernel is eaten during the month of September (when lipids content is minimal), after special religious days, 29 August - Walnut Easter. Excellent edible and technical oil is extracted from walnut kernels, which is usually used also for technical purposes: in painting, to obtain technical ink and in the preparation of numerous cosmetic and pharmaceutical products. Walnut leaves are also used differently. First of all, branches carrying fresh leaves are hung on doors during some summer religious days as a symbol of resistance, wellbeing, etc. A special tea for health

fortification is prepared from its leaves. Dried leaves are very good for hair washing and against skin diseases. As a fruit growing species, the walnut provides raw material for many purposes. At all times walnut wood in Moldova is mainly used for the production of furniture (doors, windows), parquet, different confectionary like pipes, souvenir boxes and bails etc. Walnut leaves are also used differently. First of all, branches carrying fresh leaves are hung on doors during some summer religious days as a symbol of resistance, wellbeing, for tea, etc. Walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) is a species, which is permanently studied in the frame of horticultural researchers of Rep. Moldova. The results of collaborative programs and implementation in different countries showed high ecological plasticity and adaptability of the main selected and created Moldovan varieties, considering changeable microclimatic and pedological local conditions. The evolution of walnut registration assortment also took into consideration consumers' preferences. Highlighted most of all, were the varieties with white walnut kernel, that were easy to shell and with a comparatively good taste and thin shell. Thus, the most popular varieties of walnuts in Moldova are: 'Kazacu', 'Kogalniceanu', 'Kostiujenskii', 'Kalarasskii', 'Schinosskii', 'Pescianski', 'Kojjeuti'. Actually in the commercial walnut plantations, the following varieties were used for testing: 'Chandler', 'Franquette', 'Lara', 'Femor'. It is important to notice that in the last time Chandler is more adaptable for local condition and marketing requirements. In Republic of Moldova, with the serious problems of water for irrigations, as walnut rootstocks serve the biotypes and varieties of local origin of *Juglans regia* ('Kisinevskii', 'Kostiujenskii', 'Kazacu', etc.). This species ensures a good grafting affinity with all approved local and introduced varieties. Biological (including differentiation of floral and vegetative buds, flowering and pollination) and agronomical proprieties were detailed investigated for registered and introduced varieties, including comparative behavior within the vegetal rest periods of different local competitive micro cultural areas. Main of them they are characterized by their high adaptability to diverse local environmental (edaphical and microclimatical) conditions (Comanici, 1980; Tzurcanu, 2004; Pintea, 2004, 2021). The principle trials of nut culture there are: stable productivity and nut (fruit) quality. Studies of local walnut genetic resources (Pintea et al., 2021) demonstrate that Rep. of Moldova could be considered as a "pan-population" in which the plants are able to exchange genes by wind pollination. The trees with lateral fruit bearing, founded also in natural population, makes our country important for walnut breeding and implementing this trait is very important to enhance the productivity aimed by breeders. collection, characterization, propagation and sustainable use of walnut genetic resources, assessment of the adaptive potential and phenotypic plasticity, are therefore items of considerable importance both for the preservation in situ and ex situ biodiversity and basis for the improvement of new varieties and the prevention of the extinction of genetic sources.

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Key words: *Juglans regia* L., varieties, culinary, pharmaceutical properties, furniture and wood industry, adaptability, productivity.

**LOCAL PLUM VARIETIES OF REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA FOR
BREEDING AND PRACTICAL PURPOSES**

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Culture tradition of plum (*Prunus domestica* L.) between rivers Nistru and Prut (actual Republic of Moldova) dates back to almost 2000 years ago. Processed plumes (prunes) having important socio-economic and heritage value being intensively exported. Starting from the 18-19 centuries plums there are cultivated practically in all home garden (domestic orchards). According investigations of exploration main of them are named: Vinete de Tiraspol, Rotunda-1, Bardace, Bardace 3, Bardace 5, Goldani ciornaia, Prune moldoveneti, Vinete de Valcinets, Prune moldovenesti. During the 1800 years in the territory of actual RM there were intensively established commercial plums orchards on the basis of local, as well as introduced European varieties. Factually in the RM more than 25000 private farmers there are involved in the production of fruits, especially plums. As consequence of dynamic expansion and reconversion of fruit trees plantation occurred. Of course, at the same time continue to be abandoned and lost old plum genotypes. Now practically plum (including 1-2 old varieties) grow in all local yards and orchards, dried plumes (prunes) continued to having significant socio-economic and heritage value. There are promoted significant change of the agriculture in general, that moved from the land-owner old style management to the modern intensive farming. Old catalogues of 7-10 main local nurseries listed a lot of varieties. As consequence a dynamic expansion and reconversion of fruit trees plantation occurred. Therefore, evaluation and establishment of germplasm of old local plums genotypes/varieties are indispensable. All representative accessions were selected in north and central different pomological zones of the Republic of Moldova. Major characterization characteristics of the plants and fruits of old varieties were conducted using UPOV descriptor, field evaluations were based also on IBPGR plum descriptors. Chemical evaluation of created, selected, introduced varieties and hybrids, being performed on the laboratory of biochemistry as well as in the department for Food technology. The following parameters were examined: total sugars and organic acid content, vitamin C content; soluble dry material; non soluble solids substances, total phenol content. In this study was determine main fruits characteristics such as fruit weight, firmness, titratable acid content and soluble solid substances and important phenological periods such as harvest of these genotypes. Visual survey of the phytosanitary status (first of all tolerance to PPV on fruits and leaves) was also carried out. Actually, in the Republic of Moldova plum continue to be one of the principal fruit of peasant domestic orchard, especially for vegetative propagated old varieties. In the same time there are promoted significant change of the agriculture in general, that moved from the land-owner old style management to the modern intensive farming. As consequence a dynamic expansion and reconversion of fruit trees plantation occurred. Of course, at the same time continue to be abandoned and lost old plum genotypes. Therefore, evaluation and establishment of germplasm of old local plums genotypes/varieties are indispensable. It is necessary to conduct *in situ* and *on-farm* inventories of plum genfond. It is important also to notice

that after characterization of main biological and fruits indicators we establish that differences between accessions are notable, especially concerning organoleptical and eating qualities. Main representative local plum variety there is Vinete de Moldova with short description. **Synonym:** Vengherka moldavskaia. A lot of centuries was growth (multiplicated) by shoots. Spreading: It is widespread all over in the rep. of Moldova and in the nearby regions of Romania and Ukraine. From 1998 year this cultivar is registered for large propagation in the Republic of Moldova. A d a p t e d to different soils and the moderate continental climate conditions. **Harvesting time:** fruits mature in late August and early September and in the north part of Moldova - in the middle of September. **Used value of the fruit:** of jam called 'povidla', jam, compote, sweet, brandy, but mainly for drying. **The tree:** Medium-vigorous. The crown is dense and wide-pyramidal. The scaffold branches are well-covered with fertile twigs. **Leaves:** Elliptic, medium to large size, dark green color. Younger trees have larger leaves. Leaf stem is medium thick, short to medium long, green or greenish-red color. **Flower:** Medium-large, white with elongated petals. Pistils and stamens are in the same level. Some **Physiological traits:** **Vigor:** Medium. **Blossoming:** on medium period and explosive. For one day 50 to 80% of the flowers can be opened. Self-fertile variety. **Productivity:** there are many biotypes that differ in size of the fruit and yield. **Fruit characteristics. Size and shape:** standard Vinete de Moldova fruits are small to medium, weighing approximately 19-23 g, and there are types of fruit with a mass up to 25 g. The fruit is of prolonged ovoid form with oval shape. **Fruit powder:** well defined. **Fruit skin:** dark blue color with pronounced fruit powder, moderate thin, easy to separate of flash. **Fruit flesh:** golden to green, moderate juicy, firm, sweet and sour, excellent quality. **Stone:** small, elongated shape. Stones are easily separated from fruit flesh (freestone). Significantly to notice that created in Rep Moldova plum assortment for long time there was principal for orchard establishment. In the last time the most important for fresh consumption and 1-3 month preservation there are important local with late maturation varieties Udlinennaia and Super president, obtained from controlled hybridization. In the conditions of climate changes some old local as well as new created Moldovan plum varieties (especially **Udlinennaia** and **Super president**) represent a permanent source for important genetic traits, for instance: different desirable nutritional qualities, new type of processing, good capacities for transportation and relative long time of preservation within controlled conditions. Good resistance to extreme agro-ecological conditions, resistance to economically significant harmful biologic agents also there are present.

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Key words: *Prunus domestica* L., varieties, germplasm, biological indicators, organoleptical qualities, productivity.

EFFECTIVENESS OF CARBECOL IN PREVENTING AND COMBATING POWDERY MILDEW ON VINE

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In the Republic of Moldova the perennial plantations occupy an area of about 288.9 thousand ha, including orchards - 138.9 thousand ha and vines - 150.0 thousand ha. The intensive chemicalization of the republic's agriculture in the last 30-50 years has led to an increasing volume of used agrochemicals. This did not contribute to crop growth, but only to environmental pollution and to occurrence of new species/breeds of resistant pests. The implementation of different schemes for combining biorational pesticides in integrated protection allows to reduce the number of treatments with 2-3 times while lowering energy costs with 30% - 40%. This refers especially to the protection of multiannual crops and vegetables where the frequency and volume of pesticide application is quite high. The powdery mildew (oidium) of the vine (*Uncinula necator*) ranks second place after the damage caused to the vine crop. The pathogen attacks all the aerial organs of the plant: leaves, grass shoots, bunches and berries. Crop losses due to this disease can range from 10% to 80%.

The aim of the research was to evaluate the biological efficacy of Carbecol based on potassium bicarbonate (2KHCO₃) in preventing and combating powdery mildew (*Uncinula necator*) in vines. Given the low level of toxicity and risk to the environment, this group of preparations is of particular interest as biorational fungicides. The researches were carried out during the years 2020–2021 within the institutional project no. 20.80009.5107.19: “Strengthening the capacities for forecasting and combating harmful organisms and phytosanitary risk analysis in integrated plant protection”, in the central area of the Republic of Moldova, experimental group of the Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection. The experiments were performed on Cardinal vine variety and consisted in 5 treatments applied with a portable sprinkler while the climatic conditions were favorable for the appearance and development of studied pathogen.

The experimental scheme included four variants: control, standard and two variants of Carbecol in different doses (4.0; 6.0 kg/ha). As a standard was the fungicide Kumulus DF (6.0 kg/ha), used in production. Each variant consisted of three repetitions, and each repetition with 10 hubs with the same crown parameters.

As a result of the statistical processing the highest biological efficacy was recorded at the chemical standard Kumulus, - 85.7%. In the Carbecol variant - 4.0 kg/ha, the biological efficacy constituted 72.8%, while in the Carbecol variant - 6.0 kg/ha, - 78.7%. Analyzing the obtained results, we can conclude that the biorational product Carbecol has demonstrated essential efficacy and can be used in the prevention and control of powdery mildew on vines, within the ecological system of plant protection.

Key words: *Uncinula necator*, pathogen, carbecol, fungicide, biological efficacy.

DIFFERENTIAL GENES EXPRESSION UNDER ANTERO- AND RETROGRADE CONTROL IN SUNFLOWER MICROSPOROGENESIS

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Nowadays, sunflower is among the leading crops of major importance for global food security. The economic interest of sunflower breeding is mainly determined by the production of seeds, whose biological yield can be increased by exhaustive knowledge of reproductive development. The control of pollen fertility is essential for germplasm diversification, hybrids with a high degree of heterosis obtaining and, more recently, ensuring the biosecurity of the introduction of transgenic plants into culture, as well as for the numerous researches of male gametophyte in various physiological or changeable environmental conditions. Of particular interest are the peculiarities of male gametophyte development in plants with gibberellin-induced male sterility (GA₃-IMS), a phenomenon that is not based on dysfunctions generated by the different genomic interactions. Thus, fertile inbred lines with androsterile analogs, fertility restorer lines and progeny (F₁) with restored fertility form an excellent model for research of cell communication, and being associated with AG3-IMS may elucidate the antero- and retrograde signaling processes of male gametogenesis under the gibberellins action. Previously, was provided the first evidence that sunflower with GA₃ induced male sterility is associated with a similar transcript to mitochondrial orfH522 characteristic for PET1 cytotpe. Taking into account that the GA₃-IMS phenotype is not the result of nucleocytoplasmic incompatibility it was concluded that meiosis cell division, mtDNA replication and mitogenome maintenance are not reliable. Thus, candidate genes involved in the mentioned events during sunflower microsporogenesis were assessed by RT-qPCR. In these investigations were used near-isonuclear lines, fertile SW501 with the *H. annuus* L cytoplasm and male sterile SW501CMS with *H. petiolaris* cytoplasm, Drofa F₁ hybrid and its parents. The plants were exogenously treated with GA₃ solution by spraying on developing inflorescence buds. The florets from inflorescence buds (R1-R3) were subjected to microscopical, physiological and molecular analyses. The model of additive/nonadditive genes expression was used to compare transcripts profiles between F₁ hybrid and its parents. Sterility of sunflower anthers as GA-induced response resulted from the perturbation of the endogen hormone concentration, as well as from the ability of cells to perceive this perturbation and activate the subsequent transduction pathways of cellular signals. It was ascertained various genes expression profiles related to sterility type, genetic background and stage of pollen development. All studied sunflower transcripts are gibberellin responsive and showed high degree level of co-expression. Several genes differentially expressed in sterile anthers (CMS and GA-IMS) were down-regulated, suggesting on DNA damage-responsive cell - cycle arrest, an important mechanism for the preservation of genomic stability. Also, the transcriptomic data showed more non-additive gene expression patterns in hybrids than additive revealing, often, microsporogenesis stage specificity. It is suggested that those genes whose expression changes in F₁ hybrids (non-additively) can be associated with heterosis, being involved in specific signaling pathways that could be targeted regulated. The fact that researches on the mechanism of heterosis continue to be essential as part of enhancing food production, there is considerable incentive to investigate the genomic consequences of heterotic gene pool development.

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Key words: sunflower, pollen fertility, microsporogenesis, genes expression.

**REVIEW OF PESTS OF THE FOREST PARK
"RISHCANI", CHISINAU**

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In the architecture of the city, the forest park is one of the main elements of green and suburban areas. Monitoring and control of the phytosanitary state of urban green spaces contributes both to the preservation of the appearance of the park, the species diversity of the flora and fauna of the park, and the safety of its visitors. Within the framework of the project 22.80015.7007.261T „Smart solutions and biotechnologies for the sustainable green spaces development under urban environment” we analyzed the species composition of plants in the Riscani park in Chisinau. Growing perennial plant species were identified on the designated experimental sites. The most widespread crops were selected for monitoring the phytosanitary condition, which are found not only in this park area, but also in other forest plantations in Moldova. Therefore, this work is of national importance. The main species in forest plantations, squares and parks of Moldovan cities are varieties of maple, oak, linden, elm, chestnut, etc. The studies were performed according to the traditional methods approved in the Republic of Moldova. This paper presents the results of observations for the period March-July 2022, observations are still ongoing. We have found that on the territory of the Riscani Park almost all deciduous species are affected by different types of aphids (*Aphidoidea* sp.). These are insects with piercing-sucking mouthparts and, in addition to direct negative effects, they are carriers of plant diseases. We also identified the pest of oak, the lace bug *Corythucha arcuata* (Say). In addition to oak, the bug infects chestnuts, elms, currants, hawthorn, plane trees, lilacs. The bug actively feeds on the leaf blade, polluting it with excrements. The rapid increase of the oak lace bug population leads to the complete destruction of the photosynthetic leaves tissue.

The most aggressive quercine pests are found mostly on the leaves: the insects from the fam. *Cynipidae*, the green oak moth (*Tortrix viridana*), the mottled umber (*Erannis defoliaria*), the winter moth (*Operophtera brumata*), the trumpet leaf miner (*Tischeria complanella*), and on fruits- the oak weevil (*Balaninus glandium* Marsh.).

The red pine sawfly (*Neodiprion sertifer*) was identified on conifers, which is the main pest that harms the common, Crimean and mountain pine, eating their needles. The beetle actively flies in the spring period. Its caterpillar feeds on needles. All damaged trees weaken, lose their decorative effect, reduce their growth, and begin to be populated by bark beetles. As a result, in the republic every year we observe a deterioration in the phytosanitary condition of green areas of forest park plantations in the urban environment. Poor phytosanitary condition of the crown can lead to the complete death of the tree and the reduction of green spaces. We consider it necessary to carry out phytosanitary monitoring of park plantings in order to develop a strategy and schemes for plant protection in the park areas of the republic.

Key words: plant species, diversity, fauna, pests.

**BEHAVIOR OF SOME SUNFLOWER HYBRIDS AT THE
ATTACK OF THE PATHOGEN *BOTRYTIS CINEREA* Pers.,
IN THE SOUTH-EAST AREA OF ROMANIA**

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Sunflower cultivation is an important component of the food industry. It is grown all over the world and therefore has a wide range of pathogens that can affect it. As phytosanitary treatments are not always effective and economical, the cultivation of disease-resistant hybrids is the main measure for both optimal yields and environmental protection.

Botrytis cinerea Pers. is a pathogen that causes quality depreciation of production to a wide range of plant species used in human nutrition. The pathogen attacks the sunflower seeds that lose their taste qualities, the latter being decisive in terms of using the product in the food industry.

The paper aimed to observe the behavior of some sunflower hybrids to the attack of the pathogen *Botrytis cinerea*, in the climatic conditions of the South-East area of Romania in 2021.

To make the observations, the biological material used was represented by nine hybrids created at the National Institute for Agricultural Research and Development-Fundulea, cultivated in climatic stress conditions. The experiment took place within the Agricultural Development Research Station-Braila, Chiscani Experimental Field, in 2021.

The hybrid H5 stood out through its low degree of attack of 1,41% compared to the average degree of attack of 2.27%. The weakest behavior regarding the pathogen attack was observed in the hybrid H4, with a degree of attack of 2.6%.

Key words: *Botrytis cinerea*, hybrid, stress conditions, degree of attack.

ENERGETIC CRISIS AND GRAIN SORGHUM VARIETY MODEL

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The energetic crisis occupies practically all countries in the civilization world today. Energy prices have skyrocketed. It has great influence on all activities including agriculture.

However, energy prices have no effect on global processes like the climatic changes and creation of population which can do the food crisis. The solution for the problem of alimentary deficit maybe the introduction of drought resistant cultures as sorghum.

Is known, the successful promotion of culture in long time perspective can be regulated by just autochthonous varieties and hybrids adopted for local climatic and soil conditions. Also, the effective breeding is based first of all on clear vision of variety or hybrid model. Until recently, the main requirements for autochthonous grain sorghum variety and hybrid models were precocity and big seed. But in wet years in Republic of Moldova even the ultra-precocity grain sorghum hybrids have harvest high humidity. It increases dramatically energy consumption in the post-harvest period. The single solution of this problem is the using of desiccants. They provoke seed humidity reduction in short time for harvesting. But using of desiccants maybe realized on undersized sorghum plants only.

Thus, the main requirements for autochthonous grain sorghum variety and hybrid models are precocity, big seed and undersized.

Key words: grain sorghum, hybrid model, desiccant, drought resistance.

PRELIMINARY DATA ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INVASIVE SPECIES *HALYOMORPHA HALYS* (STAL) 1855, (HEMIPTERA; PENTATOMIDAE) IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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The brown marmorated stink bug, *Halyomorpha halys* (Stal), 1855 (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) (BMSB) – an invasive species with a natural range of China, Japan, the countries of the Korean peninsula. The bug is a dangerous quarantine pest included in the Common List of quarantine facilities of the Eurasian Economic Union. In 2019, an invasive species was first discovered on the territory of the Republic of Moldova. In recent years, BMSB has been rapidly accelerating population development, supported by favourable climatic conditions for this species, as well as abundant plant food. Studies of biological features of invasive pests always have a strict local binding, so their conduct is necessary and on the territory of the Republic of Moldova.

The research was carried out both in the laboratory and in the field, on IGPPP test fields of the Republic of Moldova.

To determine the pest's survival after wintering on November 1, 2021, imago BMSB in the amount of 50 individuals were distributed in two insulated gardens and placed on an open terrace. After 140 days (the third decade of March), the count of surviving bugs after wintering was carried out with a further calculation in percentage.

When analyzing the data, we noted that the survival rate of the population after wintering exceeds 50%. The survival rate of females is 12.9% higher than that of males, which we believe will lead to a faster rate of population density.

In native conditions, we marked the period of release of the bug from the diapause from the third decade of April - the second decade of May. In the aftermath, there is a period of intensive feeding lasting from 1 to 2 weeks, and only then comes the period of mating. Visual observations have shown that BMSB females produce eggs 3-4 times within 6-13 days. The number of eggs in one egg range from 10 to 32. The fertility of one female averages 96 eggs (68-124).

Thus, based on the preliminary data we proved that in the agroclimatic conditions of the Republic of Moldova, this species can develop favorably and can cause economically important crop losses of various crops.

Acknowledgments: Research was carried out within the project of the State Program 20.80009.5107.27 “Elaboration of the alternative methods based on environmentally friendly means and procedures for harmful arthropods control in different agricultural crops”, financed by the National Agency for Research and Development.

Key words: *Halyomorpha halys*, invasive specie, wintering, survival, fertility.

**SCREENING FOR HEAT-RESISTANCE OF POLLEN IN PROGENY OF
VIRUS-INFECTED TOMATO GENOTYPES**

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The reaction of the male gametophyte of virus-infected tomato plants is differentiated under conditions of high temperature. At the same time, information on the heat resistance of the progeny of these genotypes is limited. The aim of the research was to study the effect of high temperature on the variability of the male gametophyte of the progeny of plants infected with TMV (*Tobacco Mosaic Virus*) or TAV (*Tomato Aspermy Virus*).

An assessment of the thermal resistance of the male gametophyte of healthy plants and progeny of virus-infected plants revealed, on average, the highest level of this trait in control plants – 62.5%. The level of the thermal resistance in TMV/TAV progeny was lower, by 13.3% and 22.2 %, respectively. Differences in the length of pollen tubes were also established between the control and experimental variants. In TMV/TAV progeny, as in the case of pollen viability, a decrease in the length of pollen tubes was observed by 32.9% and 28.4%, respectively, compared to the control. This result can probably be determined by the lower growth rate of the pollen tubes in these genotypes.

It has been established that the male gametophyte of control plants and progeny of virus-infected plants of varieties Mihaela, Rufina and the wild species *S. pimpinellifolium* combines a high level of heat resistance of pollen viability and pollen tubes length, which suggests the prospect of their use in further research.

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the NARD (project 20.80009.7007.04 "Biotechnologies and genetical processes for evaluation, conservation and exploitation of agrobiodiversity").

Key words: tomato, TMV, heat resistance, pollen.

PHAGE EFFICIENT AGAINST FIRE BLIGHT AND FRUIT TREES BACTERIAL CANKER PATHOGENS

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Fire blight and bacterial canker of apple, pear and quince, the economically most important diseases of fruit trees, are caused by the bacterial phyto-pathogens *Erwinia amylovora* and *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *syringae*, respectively. *E. amylovora* and *Ps. syringae* pv. *syringae* are often present together in the aerial parts of plants and in the most cases both bacteria are detected in the same plant samples. Currently available bacteriosis control agents as, e.g., copper preparations or antibiotics act mostly unspecifically and are prone to resistance development. Alternative disease management strategies are, therefore, highly solicited.

Bacteriophages, i.e. highly specific bacterial viruses that infect and lyse bacteria, are under intensive evaluation as the biocontrol agents. The advantage of phages is that they are natural components of ecosystems, infect only bacteria sensitive to them and are non-toxic to plants, animals and humans.

Phages, infecting *E. amylovora* and *Ps. syringae* pv. *syringae* known up to now belong to the taxonomic families *Podoviridae*, *Myoviridae*, and *Siphoviridae*.

When studied the ability of phages isolated in the quince orchard to infect cells of fire blight and bacterial canker causative agents one phage was detected to be able to lyse both pathogens. A major capsid protein based multiplex PCR assay used for phage identification revealed that the isolated phage belongs to the Y2 group, which includes *Myoviridae* phages. Some of the representatives of the Y2 group are the broad host range phages. By pulsed-field gel electrophoresis analysis genome size of the phage was determined.

After a detailed study of biological effectiveness, the isolated bacteriophage could be used for biocontrol of the fire blight and bacterial canker pathogens.

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Key words: phytopathogen, multiplex PCR assay, bacterial canker.

THE IMPACT OF THE PRUNING SYSTEM ON THE SWEET CHERRY TREE GROWTH AND FRUCTIFICATION

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The formation of crowns of sweet cherry trees, the pruning time and the existing growing technologies that allow the maximum use of the biological potential of modern gardens remain relevant. Along with the classical methods (rootstock, variety, fertilization, irrigation, etc.) of regulating the growth and fruiting of sweet cherry trees, the pruning during the growing season is a process of improving the physiological balance between the vegetative growth and the number of fruits. The pruning of trees in early autumn, namely in the first decade of September, in contrast with the conventional pruning carried out when the trees enter the dormant period, has a greater impact on yield and fruit size. As a general trend, the pruning during the growing season leads to an increase in the size and colour of the fruit and to a decrease in the incidence of brown rot. It is increasingly used in high density orchards.

The purpose of the research was to evaluate the impact of the time of the pruning of the sweet cherry trees of Kordia, Regina, Stella, Ferrovia and Skeena varieties, grafted on the Maxima 14 rootstock, on the yield and quality of sweet cherries (*Prunus avium* L.). The orchard was laid out with 3 m between trees in the row, and 5 m between rows. The canopy of the trees was small and of a naturally improved shape. The maintenance and thinning pruning of the sweet cherry trees were done during both the growing season and the dormant period. The pruning system consisted of four time periods: G1 – Pruning during the dormancy (control group), G2 – Pruning during the flowering period; G3 – Post-harvest pruning; G4 – Pruning in early autumn. Four groups of eight trees each were used in the experiment.

The orchard was irrigated using the drip irrigation system. Water was distributed by droppers fixed at a height of 40 cm from the ground in the direction of the row. The soil was kept artificially grassed. The weeds on the two-meter-wide strips of land between the rows were mowed down as needed and left as mulch. The grass of natural or artificial growth, which grew on the strips 2-2.5 m wide between the rows of trees, was mowed as needed and left as mulch. The weeds were killed with herbicides applied along the rows, or mechanically weeded twice or thrice times using sensitive weeding equipment.

The pruning of sweet cherry trees is a process, which has a great impact on the fruit quality and yield. The pruning time had a strong impact on the growth and fructification of the cherry tree varieties grown in an intensive farming system. The pruning done during the growing season (the post-harvest pruning and the pruning in early autumn) had a greater impact on the tree vegetative growth, i.e. the height of the tree, the average and total length of annual branches, and the section of the trunk. The sweet cherry trees of the Kordia, Regina, Stella, Ferrovia and Skeena varieties, grafted on the rootstock Maxima 14, in G 4 (the pruning was done in early autumn) formed fruit branches with a large number of flower buds, over against G1 in which the pruning was done during the dormant period (the control group).

Key words: *Prunus avium* L., fruit quality, pruning time, growth

**THE IMPACT OF THE CROWN SHAPE ON THE GROWTH
AND FRUCTIFICATION OF CHERRY TREE VARIETIES
GROWN IN AN INTENSIVE SYSTEM**

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In the Republic of Moldova, new varieties of cherry trees grafted on semi dwarfing rootstocks (Gisela 5, Krymsk 6), moderate vigor rootstocks (MaxMa 14, Piku 1, Piku 4) and semi vigorous rootstocks (Gisela 6, PHL-C, Krymsk 6) are cultivated. Dwarfing rootstocks have made it possible to grow high density orchards of small trees, which are more productive and develop earlier. Fertile well-irrigated soils are used to grow trees grafted on the above-mentioned rootstocks. Medium-sized trees, which can be fully tended from the ground, provide early average yield of fruit and reduce fruit harvesting costs by increasing the harvesting productivity. Since the use of dwarfing (Gisela 5, Krymsk 6), moderate vigour (MaxMa Delbard 14, Piku 1, Piku 4) and semi vigorous (Gisela 6, P HL-C, Krymsk 6) rootstocks, the need has arisen to use small crown trees as well. As the result of this fact, the impact of the crown shape on the productivity of the Early Star, Samba and Black Star varieties, grafted on Gisela 6 was studied.

The aim of the research was to increase the productivity of sweet cherry orchards by identifying highly productive crown shapes for the Early Star, Samba and Black Star varieties, grafted on Gisela 6, suitable for the Republic of Moldova. The researches were carried out in the central orcharding area of the Republic of Moldova, at the StarAgroGroop Ltd., between the years 2018-2021. The impact of the crown shape on the growth and fructification of the Early Star, Samba and Black Star cherry tree varieties, grafted on the rootstock Gisela 6, was studied. The trees were established in 2015. The orchard had a planting density of 1250 trees/ha. The crowns of the trees were of improved thin spindle shape, and of Cup and Kym Green Bush shape. The orchard was irrigated using the drip irrigation system and fertilized using foliar applications of urea and microelements to fruit trees. The soil on the rows of trees was artificial grassed and treated with herbicides. The weeds on the two-meter-wide strips of land between the rows were mowed down as needed and left as mulch.

The fruit yield varied greatly depending on the late spring frosts during the opening of the buds and the flowering of the cherry trees, the variety and the shape of the crown. In 2019, the Samba variety cherry trees produced the best crop, namely 16.8 t/ha, by 56.4-139.9 % larger than the Early Star and Samba varieties. In 2020, the Black Star variety produced a rich harvest of 10.3 t/ha, which was 111.4-151.4% larger than the Early Star and Samba varieties. In 2021, the Samba variety stood out with the highest harvest (10.3-16.2 t/ha) followed by the Early Star variety (7.7-9.4 t/ha) and Black Star (3.7-5.5 t/ha). The highest yield on average over three years was obtained from the trees with improved thin spindle crowns as compared to the cupped and Kim Green Bush crowned trees. In the first four years of their fruiting, the fruit harvest in the Samba variety was significantly higher as opposed to the Early Star and Black Star varieties.

Key words: variety, productivity, sweet cherry, orchard, growth.

EVALUATION OF *SOPHORA FLAVESCENS* EXTRACT FOR COMBAT THE RED MITE (*TETRANYCHUS URTICAE*) TO THE TOMATO CROP IN GREENHOUSE

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Intensive use of increased amounts of chemicals in the agricultural sector for the treatment of tomato crops in greenhouse, led to a demand for organic products on the market. The need to reduce crop losses raises the issue of developing effective plant protection measures that reduce the dynamics of the development of harmful organisms with a minimum number of chemical treatments. Tomato crops in greenhouse suffer huge losses due to damage caused by red mite. This pest can be present throughout the vegetation period if various preventive measures are not taken in time. The aim of this article is to demonstrate the biological efficacy of *Sophora flavescens* plant extract in controlling mites in tomato crops. For this purpose three variants were installed. The first variant was witness, the second variant (standard) the insecticide Pelecol 0.8 l/ha, the third variant was used the extract from *Sophora flavescens*. 14 l/ha. No treatment was applied to the witness plants, so the development of mites was very rapid. Each of the variants had 3 repetitions. The degree of attack and the intensity of development were determined according to the method described by A. Hrapova (Roșca *et al.*, 1996). The first treatment was performed on 13.06.2022. Before testing the extracts on tomato plants, 12-26 mites were registered on the leaf. The application of the treatment contributed to the mortality of the pest both on the plants from the variant of the tested preparation and on the one from the standard variant.

Evaluating the data obtained after treatment, a decrease in the number of pests was observed in relation to the untreated plant. Thus, the biological efficacy of *Sophora flavescens* extract after the 3rd, 7th and 14th day on average was 80%, in the Etalon variant, it was 91%. From these data it results that the treatment of tomato plants with *Sophora flavescens* plant extract reduces the spread of mites, although it has demonstrated a slightly lower biological efficacy compared to the standard.

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Key words: *Sophora flavescens*, plant extract, biological efficacy, tomato, red mite.

INFLUENCE OF MINOR COMPONENTS ON THE EFFICIENCY OF APPLE WORM SEX PHEROMONE

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The apple worm is the main pest of apple trees, leading to losses of up to 70-90% of production. Today, there is an intensive development of organic farming in the world. In this regard, the development of non-invasive methods and environmentally friendly products used in the biological protection of plants, including through the use of sex pheromone traps, is of major importance for agricultural producers worldwide. The use of approved pheromone-based preparations can minimize population density, which is extremely important for the production of a rich harvest of ecologically pure products. The role of minor components found in the literature is currently being investigated, for example, different authors list up to thirteen components for the apple pheromone sex pheromone, where their ratio varies in different compositions. In our work, we studied the effect of two minor components on the effectiveness of the codling moth sex pheromone.

In the laboratory "Integrated Plant Protection", within the IGPPP, the main component E8,E10-12:OH was synthesized and variants with different two-component pheromone compositions were prepared where the minor component dodecanol (C₁₂H₂₅OH) was added to the synthesized basic component in the amount of 5%, 10%, 30%, 60%, and the minor component tetradecanol (C₁₄H₂₉OH) in the amount of 3%, 6%, 12%, respectively, which were subsequently impregnated on rubber septas, according to the scheme of experiments, with the formation of pheromone sets on variants, composed of the delta-shaped trap body, sticky plate and rubber septa.

In 2020, experiments were performed in the apple orchard of the Scientific - Practical Institute of Horticulture and Food Technologies in Codru town. The observations were made with an interval of 5-7 days, the sticky plates were changed once in 15 days. From the obtained data it was found that the use of dodecanol as a minor component in the pheromone composition increased its biological efficacy. In variants where 60% and 30% of the minor component dodecanol were added, the average male catches increased by 56% and 62% respectively. An analogous trend in the use of the minor component tetradecanol was observed. In this case, the number of males caught in delta-traps with pheromone compositions where 12% and 6% of tetradecanol were added, increased by 29 - 35%, the statistical analysis did not confirm the differences observed due to the variability of the data obtained. In this way, a significant positive effect of the influence of minor components in two-component pheromone compositions was observed.

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Key words: apple worm, pheromone, dodecanol, tetradecanol, biological efficacy.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELATIVE MATURITY AND GRAIN YIELD IN EXPERIMENTED NEW MAIZE HYBRIDS

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Very variable weather in the current changing climatic conditions, affects the establishment of the vegetation period of crops and exposes crops to failure, if farmers choose crops that are not adapted to relative maturity and that do not match the characteristics of the growing period.

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the relative maturity of maize hybrids and grain yield and to determine the period of relative maturity that will support grain production in corn. In this experiment, a set of maize hybrids with different relative maturity were cultivated within the Institute of Crop Science „Porumbeni”, in the years 2020-2021. The total number of 200 maize hybrids were grouped into 4 maturity groups, entitled confirmed an approved native hybrid, depending on the relative maturity that ranged from 119 to 135 days. Maize hybrids were grown in optimal growing conditions. From the results obtained, it was observed that the control hybrids had a very low grain yield compared to the new hybrids experienced. In the first group, where 13 new hybrids were tested, the control hybrid Porumbeni 310, had 120 days until the relative maturation, and the grain yield was the lowest, namely 78.5%. In this group the new hybrids had from 119 to 124 days to full maturity, and the grain yield varied from 81.03% to 88.7%, which we can say that the grain yield of new hybrids was higher than the control, on average by 7.0%. The second group included 43 new hybrids and a control hybrid Porumbeni 374. The control hybrid had 122 days until full maturation and a grain yield of 80.7%, that is, 3% lower than the yield of newly experienced hybrids. The relative maturation of the hybrids in the second group varied between 124 and 128 days, 3 days longer than the control hybrid. The grain yield of new hybrids in this group was from 78.8% to 88.5%. The third group registered 45 new hybrids and the control hybrid Porumbeni 427. The number of days until full maturation was 127-132 days, depending on the year of experimentation, and the control hybrid recorded 125 days until maturation. The grain yield in new hybrids ranged from 78.5% to 87.6%, while the control hybrid had a yield of 80.8%, lower on average by 4%, compared to the grain yield in new hybrids. The newly tested hybrids, the fourth maturity group, were witnessed by the local hybrid Porumbeni 461, which recorded 130 days until full maturation and a grain yield of 77.9%, and which was the lowest grain yield, from all experienced hybrids. In contrast, the new hybrids tested in this group had full maturation from 129 days to 135 days, and the grain yield ranged from 78.6% to 87.5%, which is 6% higher than the grain yield recorded at the control hybrid.

On average, we recorded full maturation in the first group at 120 days, in the second group at 125 days, in the third group at 128 days and in the fourth group at 130 days. The average grain yield in each group was 84.6% in the first group, 83.6% for the second group, 83.9% in the third group and 83.6% in the fourth group, respectively. So, we can say that the obtained results showed an insignificant increase in grain yield in earlier maturing hybrids and an insignificant decrease in grain yield in later hybrids.

This experiment showed that relative maturity had an insignificant impact on grain yield in maize hybrids, however, medium and semilate maturing hybrids had low grain yields.

Key words: hybrid, maize, maturation, grain yield.

BIOPESTICIDES - AN ALTERNATIVE AND ECO-FRIENDLY SOURCE FOR THE CONTROL OF PESTS

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Chemical pesticides are widely used worldwide but they are ecologically unacceptable. Use of chemical pesticides has resulted in the disturbance of our environment (Gulhane *et al.*, 2015). Due to the side effects of chemical pesticides, sustainable crop production through eco-friendly management is essentially required in the current scenario the biopesticides is ecofriendly pest control pesticides (Hubbard *et al.*, 2014). Presently, about 8.5% of EU's agricultural area is farmed organically, and the trends show that with the present growth rate, the EU will reach 15-18% by 2030.

The global biopesticides market is projected to grow at a CAGR of 14.7% from an estimated value of USD 4.3 billion in 2020 to reach USD 8.5 billion by 2025. Widely used biopesticides are living organisms which are mostly pathogenic for the target species only These biopesticides are good alternatives to conventional insecticides for sustainable management of insect pests (Prabha *et al.*, 2016).

The present paper gives information of *Bacillus thuringiensis* ssp. kurstaki preparats, we discuss how evolution, host range determination and pathogenesis have contributed to their inherent safety for non-target organisms including humans. The entomopathogenic microorganismsalso can accumulate themselves in the environment and the host population, and it can control the pest insects for a long term by forming epidemic disease in the pest insect population through the external environment stimulation. The quite stable food chain relation of plant-pest insect- natural enemy can be gradually established. Thus, it can reduce the risk of the pest insect continuous outbreak and realize the persistent control of pest insects.

Bacillus thuringiensis (Bt) are bacteria found naturally in the environments of every continent of the world. Some of the Bt strains are natural antagonists of some pests. A few Bt strains have been selected and commercialized as biological pest control products. These commercialized Bt strains are valuable to agriculture and public health because of their unique ability to naturally control certain destructive and disease-carrying insect pests while avoiding harm to non-target organisms (such as beneficial insects, people, other mammals, and fish). Biological insect control products based on Bt strains have been used safely and effectively in practical field conditions for more than 50 years.

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Key words: *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt), biopesticide, pathogenesis, target specie, pest.

**BIO-ECOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF SOME NEW TAXA OF
BERBERIS THUNBERGII DC.**

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The implementation of the Global Biodiversity Strategy aims at a series of high-priority goals, one of them being the enrichment and diversification of the gene pool in green spaces. The representatives of the genus *Berberis* L. are high-value honey and ornamental plants. The genus *Berberis* L. belongs to the family *Berberidaceae* Juss. The genus *Berberis* L. includes about 175 species and a very large diversity of taxa. They occur in the temperate zone of Europe, Asia and North America. Thirty-one species and several varieties occur in the Republic of Moldova. In the last 4-5 years, in the "Alexandru Ciubotaru" National Botanical Garden (Institute) (hereinafter NBGI), 24 new taxa of Japanese barberry, bred in Poland, have been introduced and need to be researched, assessed bioecologically under the new growth conditions for further use. The goal of this research included the identification of the bioecological peculiarities of 4 *Berberis de thunbergii* DC. taxa – ‘Maria’, ‘Green Cloud’, ‘Red Torch’, ‘Dart’s Red Lady’ under new *ex-situ* conditions and the appreciation of the prospects of their use in landscaping.

The research was conducted in 2019-2022 in the plant nursery of the Dendrology Laboratory, within the project 20.80009.7007.19 "The introduction and development of technologies for propagation and cultivation of new species of woody plants by conventional techniques and tissue culture". The respective taxa, which grow in the collection of NBGI, are currently in the third and fourth growing season. The morphological parameters were determined for 10 plants of each taxon, as well as for 100 flowers and shoots. The frequency of flowers and fruits per 20-cm-long shoot and the fruit yield were determined in the fourth growing season. The researched taxa are tolerant to drought, frost, noxious substances; they do not require special care, only regular trimming to keep their shape and compliance with standard technology throughout the growing season. The studied shrubs are particularly showy in early spring, due to the beautiful yellow colour of the flowers, the abundance of flowering, the density of flowers and shoots per 20-cm-long shoot, as well as in early summer – due to the shade of the foliage, the shape and size of the plant and fruits and the various colors of the fruits (red, orange-red, purple-red), the abundance of fruiting, the long period of flowering and fruiting.

The studied taxa differ significantly in plant height, which varied from 36 cm in *Berberis thunbergii* ‘Green Cloud’ to 114 cm in *Berberis thunbergii* ‘Red Torch’. They also differ in crown diameter, which ranged from 50-52 cm (in the taxa *B. th.* ‘Maria’, *B. th.* ‘Green Cloud’) to 70-72 cm (*B. th.* ‘Red Torch’, ‘Dart’s Red Lady’). The density of fruits per 20-cm-long shoot varied from 2 pcs. (*B. m.* ‘Dart’s Red Lady’) to 14 pcs. (*B. th.* ‘Red Torch’). The taxon *B. th.* ‘Red Torch’ is characterized by a high percentage of fruit bearing (80.1%), *B. th.* ‘Dart’s Red Lady’ – 30.6%, and the other taxa have intermediate values of this index. The fruit bearing percentage correlates with both the biotype and the climatic conditions during the process of ontomorphogenesis.

Key words: *Berberis thunbergii*, morphological parameters, biotype, growing season, period of flowering and fruiting.

**TRANSCRIPTOME ANALYSIS AND RESISTANCE GENE MINING OF
SUNFLOWER RESISTANT *OROBANCHE CUMANA* RACE G**

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Orobanche cumana (sunflower broomrape) is an obligatory, non-photosynthetic root parasitic plant that specifically infects the sunflower. Broomrape causes severe yield losses of sunflower. In order to control broomrape infestation, some resistance genes are being uncovered by our RNA-seq analysis. In this study, two sunflower varieties (resistant/sensitive sandaomei strain) were selected and inoculated with broomrape respectively. During the interaction between sunflower and broomrape, sunflower roots were sampled at germination stage, small nodule stage and large nodule stage, and transcriptome sequencing was performed. We finally deployed the Deseq2 assay to screen differentially expressed genes between resistant cultivars and sensitive cultivars. A total of 2,058 differentially expressed genes were obtained during germination stage, including 1093 up-regulated genes and 965 down-regulated genes. A total of 1541 differentially expressed genes were obtained at small nodule stage, including 867 up-regulated genes and 674 down-regulated genes. A total of 1231 differentially expressed genes were obtained at large nodule stage, including 327 up-regulated genes and 904 down-regulated genes.

The KEGG enrichment analysis showed that the up-regulated genes were mainly enriched in the Ras signaling pathway, Phenylpropanoid biosynthesis, Plant-pathogen interaction, Plant-pathogen interaction, MAPK signaling pathway, and these pathways related to resistance response in the germination stage and down-regulated genes mainly focus on Phenylalanine metabolism, Pentose and glucuronate interconversions. At the small nodule stage, the up-regulated genes mainly enriched in Ras signaling pathway, Aldosterone synthesis and secretion. The down-regulated genes mainly focus on Phenylpropanoid biosynthesis, Pentose and glucuronate interconversions, p53 signaling pathway. At the large nodule stage, the up-regulated genes mainly enriched in Metabolism of xenobiotics by cytochrome P450, beta - Alanine metabolism, beta-Alanine metabolism. The down-regulated genes mainly focus on Ras signaling pathway, Cutin, suberine and wax biosynthesis. Ras Signaling Pathway was up-regulated at germination stage and small nodule stage, and down-regulated at large nodule stage, indicating that this pathway was the key signaling pathway for sunflower resistance to broomrape.

Key words: *Orobanche cumana*, varietie, transcriptome, sequencing, gene expression, germination stage, metabolism.

FIELD RESISTANCE OF SUNFLOWER VARIETIES RESOURCES TO SEED RUST SPOTS DISEASE

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Sunflower seed rust is an emerging disease found in the production in recent years. The disease is characterized by irregular rust spots on sunflower husk. Its occurrence had seriously affected sunflower appearance for seeds serving, and was becoming a bottleneck for sunflower industry. Field experiments were carried out in Wulateqian County and Wuyuan County in Bayannur, Inner Mongolia, China. In these areas, sunflower seeds suffered seriously. The resistance to seed rust spots was evaluated on 44 sunflower cultivars, including 39 confectionery sunflowers and 5 oil sunflowers. The diseased scales (0~4) were scored based on following criterion. level 0 = No rust spot of seeds on the whole capitulum, level 1 =Rust spots on the seed surface of all rust-spotted seeds account for an average of 1% to 25%, level 2 =The proportion is an average of $\geq 25\%$, level 3= The proportion is an average of $\geq 50\%$, level 4 = The proportion is an average of $\geq 75\%$. Seed rust spot rate (%) = number of rust spots on seeds / number of seeds $\times 100$. For each varieties, three replications with 15 plants were scored.

Results showed that, among the confectionery sunflowers in Wulateqian County, rate of seed rust spots of Sairui 1 was the lowest ($< 25\%$). 6 varieties had lower rates between 25% and 50% (such as JK 103, LJ 188, LD 5009, etc.), the others were more than 50%. Considering the severity levels, 20 varieties were in level 1, but with the disease rate ranging from 17.30% to 88.63%. In Wuyuan County, the disease rate was 61.02% to 99.63%, significantly higher than the same varieties in Wulateqian County, but with lower level. Only 10 varieties were in level 1 such as 3638C. For oil sunflower, 4 varieties were lower than 25%, except for XKS2029. In addition, rust occurrence of the same variety at different sowing times also showed significant differences. For example, for SH361, the rate was 34.49% on the sowing date of May 27th, but 98.47% on June 20th. It indicated that different sowing dates effected the occurrence of seed rust spots.

Keywords: sunflower, seed, disease, varietie, rust.